

Demonstration of effluent reuse and treatment of off spec raw water with reverse osmosis

Deliverable 2.6

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Summary

D2.9 outlines the work conducted in Task T2.3 (Water-smart solutions for Flanders), focusing on Subtask 2.3.1 “Demonstration of effluent reuse and treatment of off spec raw water with reverse osmosis”. The original Description of Work (DoW) referred to Aquifer Storage and Recovery (ASR), but as agreed in amendment 1 the work was changed from ASR to the use of off spec raw water with reverse osmosis with a specific focus on a high water recovery rate. Within WP2.3.1 two pilots were run to assess respectively the potential of a closed circuit reverse osmosis unit (CCRO) for treatment of off spec raw water and the reuse of effluent from a municipal waste water treatment plant in Woumen. The report provides detailed information on the case study, process units, and operational parameters.

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History of change

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1.0	31/5/2024	Submission	-
2.0	24/10/2024	History of changes was added to the document	History of changes
		Elaborate on conducted QMRA	Annex 1
		Cost-benefit analysis	Section 5.4
		Minor layout issues	-

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

GAC	Granular Activated Carbon
AOP	advanced oxidation process
BAC	biologically active activated carbon filter
CC	Closed circuit
CCRO	Closed Circuit Reverse Osmosis
CIP	Cleaning in Place
DAF	dissolved air flotation
DALY	Disability-adjusted life years
EC	Electrical conductivity
EDS	Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy
GAC	Granular Activated Carbon
MBR	membrane bioreactor
MF	Microfiltration
NF	Nanofiltration
NPF	Normalized Permeate Flow
NPOC	Non Purgeable Organic Carbon
NSP	Normalized Salt Passage
OMP	Organic Micropollutant
PF	Plug Flow
QMRA	Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment
RO	Reverse Osmosis
SBS	Sodium bisulfite
SDI	Silt Density Index
SEC	Specific energy consumption (kWh/m ³)
SEM	Scanning electron spectroscopy
SF	Sand Filtration
TCF	Temperature Correction Factor

TDS Total Dissolved Solids

TLR Technology Readiness Level

TMP Transmembrane Pressure

TOC Total Organic Carbon

UF Ultrafiltration

UV Ultraviolet

VMM Vlaams Milieu Maatschappij (Flemish Environment Agency)

WAVE Water Application Value Engine; simulation software from DuPont

WP Work Package

WPC Water Production Centre

WTP Water treatment plant

WWTP Waste water treatment plant

UWWTD Urban Waste water Treatment Directive

Executive summary

Flanders faces water challenges as a result of a combination of high drinking water demand due to the population density, high irrigation demand for agriculture, groundwater overexploitation, water quality deterioration, water scarcity caused by droughts and climate change. The drinking water production facility De Blankaart of De Watergroep (Diksmuide, BE) produces drinking water from surface water. At the drinking water production facility, water availability is limited due to seasonal impact and surface water quality deterioration. Even if ample surface water is available in the region, the water quality may not fulfil the intake specifications actually defined by De Watergroep to secure drinking water quality of the treatment. This is called off spec surface water.

Within B-WaterSmart, two options are evaluated to overcome the actual water scarcity:

- **CCRO** for treatment of off spec surface water
- Treatment of **WWTP effluent** as an alternative raw water source.

To evaluate the use of **off spec surface water**, it was decided to operate first a small-scale pilot to get familiar with RO technology prior to installing a demo scale and more complex RO pilot. With the small-scale pilot, a first element test was conducted to investigate fouling and to select the optimal position of the RO technology within the existing drinking water production line. It was decided to test a large scale pilot unit after the sand filtration step. After a market consultation, a **Closed Circuit Reverse Osmosis (CCRO)** technology was selected. CCRO differs from conventional RO systems by a cyclic operational mode. Main benefits are a higher flexibility towards varying incoming water quality, low sensitivity for scaling and high water recovery ([CCRO \(lenntech.nl\)](https://www.lenntech.nl)). Especially a high water recovery is a key success factor for De Watergroep given the water scarcity and limited storage capacity. In the period September 2022 until June 2023 a CCRO pilot (10 m³/h) was operated at the water production plant of the Blankaart, Diksmuide. The water recovery of the CCRO was gradually increased from 85% to 95%. Even at this high water recovery the CCRO process remained stable and no indications of scaling were observed. The chloride retention was about 90% and micropollutants (pesticides, pharmaceuticals, PFAS) were retained to concentrations below drinking water standards. Especially the high water recovery is essential for successful integration. The study was not conclusive on the specific energy consumption (SEC). Although CCRO claims to be more energy efficient compared to reverse osmosis, this claim could not be validated due to technical limitations of the pilot.

To evaluate the use of **WWTP effluent** as raw water source for drinking water another pilot unit was installed at the WWTP of Woumen. The pilot consisted of several treatment technologies, organized in modules:

- Prefiltration and ultrafiltration (UF)
- Reverse osmosis (RO)
- Granular activated carbon (GAC) and ultraviolet disinfection (UV)

- Chemical dosage

The full treatment train therefore consisted of UF-RO-GAC-UV. The treatment train can be modified to test different combinations of technologies, by bypassing individual modules. Initially frequent fouling of the prefiltration step occurred. Both technical issues and the presence of cationic polymers applied to enhance settling in the waste water treatment plant supposedly contributed to the observed fouling. Additionally, the ineffective prefiltration caused irreversible fouling of the ultrafiltration membranes. After modification of the prefiltration, replacing the ultrafiltration membranes and replacing the cationic polymer by an anionic polymer, the pilot unit could be restarted. However, due to an extreme flooding event in the region during autumn 2023, the pilot test had to be stopped. Due to the technical issues and the regional flooding, the pilot unit could only be operated stably during a limited period of time. The following conclusions could be drawn for the pilot tests:

- Activated carbon as stand-alone technology is insufficient to remove the micropollutants to allow using the treated water as source for drinking water.
- The combination of ultrafiltration and reverse osmosis can reduce the concentrations of chlorides and micropollutants below intake standards for the drinking production site of the Blankaart.

Although all used technologies are of TRL 9, their application on secondary effluent appeared to be very challenging, mainly concerning clogging and fouling of prefiltration and ultrafiltration. Given the short time of operation, operation conditions (flux, water recovery, energy consumption...) could not be optimized. The report formulates recommendations to avoid the technical challenges in further pilot tests or full-scale installations.

To evaluate the impact of an additional treatment step and/or alternative feed water, a **model** was built. The model takes into account historical data for the period 1/1/2015 until 31/7/2023) related to water availability and water quality at the two main water sources for WPC De Blankaart. Intake restrictions are imposed for the parameters chlorides, bentazon and metaldehyde. The model calculates the mass balance over the reservoir on a daily basis. The model predicts the water level in the reservoir over time. A minimum level of 700,000 m³ in the reservoir is considered as a critical level for the water production. In the actual situation the model predicts that this critical level is reached in 4 out of 8 years considered. This can be overcome largely with the additional CCRO treatment. Given the higher intake criteria (less stringent due to additional CCRO), water intake is possible for a longer period in spring and sometimes additional water intake is possible in summertime.

Similar to the CCRO scenario described above, the use of WWTP effluent enables to maintain the drinking water production. Although the impact of both scenarios is comparable, the mechanism is different. The CCRO enables to prolong the intake period of freshwater. When WWTP effluent is applied, the intake period for freshwater is unchanged and the decreasing tendency starts at the

same moment compared with the no action situation. However, as about 5,000 m³/day external water becomes available, less water needs to be extracted from the reservoir. The slope of the decrease changes and water production from the reservoir can continue over a longer period.

Both scenarios contribute to a more robust drinking water production in the region. However, the model indicates that for scenario 1 (treatment of off spec water by CCRO) the installed capacity should be designed for a capacity of 20,000 m³/day. A comparable impact can be achieved with a smaller unit (5,000 m³/day) for scenario 2 (use of WWTP effluent). Economically, the second scenario is therefore preferred.

The use of reverse osmosis technology generates in both cases a concentrate stream. The discharge of this concentrate stream may be subjected to discharge limitations and may require additional brine treatment. This aspect was not part of the work program of B-WaterSmart and will be evaluated in a follow-up project.

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduction to the problem

Flanders faces water challenges as a result of a combination of high drinking water demand due to the dense population, high irrigation demand for agriculture, groundwater overexploitation, water quality deterioration, water scarcity caused by droughts and climate change. The drinking water production facility De Blankaart of De Watergroep (Diksmuide, BE) produces drinking water from surface water. At the drinking water production facility, water availability is limited due to seasonal impact and surface water quality deterioration. Due to seasonally high concentrations of chlorides, nitrates, and organic micropollutants, the surface water quality is often insufficient for upgrading to drinking water with the existing conventional treatment steps.

Within B-WaterSmart, it is investigated whether a lower dependence on the raw water quality can be achieved by means of a Reverse Osmosis (RO) installation or by addressing WWTP effluent as an alternative raw water source. RO results in extensive removal of chlorides, increasing the performance of the installation and thus making the intake specifications for raw water to the reservoir less strict. Addressing alternative water sources reduces dependency on surface water. The goal is to increase the availability of drinking water. As such, drinking water robustness could be increased at a regional scale.

A feasibility study (VITO/De Watergroep, June 2020) already showed theoretically that adding RO as a treatment step could result in increased water availability. Within B-WaterSmart, pilot testing is conducted to demonstrate the feasibility of RO in practice and to explore the potential of WWTP effluent reuse.

1.2 Regional solutions

One might question the sustainability of the RO solution for drinking water production since it consumes energy and also produces concentrate. These concerns are valid and should not be ignored. For the moment, De Watergroep has more than 90 drinking water production facilities and none has RO, proving this technology is not the first choice, nor is the sustainability overlooked when thinking of solutions. The choice to experiment here with RO is due to necessity, since the regional context makes it very difficult to opt for other solutions:

- There is an existing surface water treatment facility of 40,000 m³/day with an extensive treatment train;
- The intake buffer is limited to 3 x 10⁶ m³ and it is very unlikely that this can be expanded (since it is situated in a Special Protection Area based on the EU-Birds Directive);
- The deteriorating surface water quality limits the raw water intake at an increasing ratio

which results in restricted production volumes.

- There is no groundwater available.
- There is no option for subsurface water storage and recovery (ASR).

Since there is no option to increase the buffer capacity (storing raw water with a good quality as provided during winter) and closing the installation is also not an option (alternatives are missing), only a limited number of options were identified for this site:

1. Improving the chloride and micropollutant removal to improve the water availability (short-term);
2. Improving the raw water quality (long-term);
3. Improving the buffer capacity (feasible?);
4. Exploring alternative sources for intake water.

As explained, options 2 and 3 are very difficult since these options are highly dependent on external entities and can only be seen as long-term achievable. However, De Watergroep is doing efforts, especially in option 2, since we are involved in projects looking for regional improved water management (other alternatives are looked at) as well as e.g. looking at possibilities to create a central brine collector for both industrial and drinking water companies to connect to their water reuse projects, zero liquid discharge technology etc. Therefore, the option for RO must be seen as a solution contributing towards a more robust drinking water production, yet embedded in a more regional strategy and not as a promotion for this technology or an isolated demonstration opportunity.

Option 4, the use of alternative sources of intake water, was studied in more detail within B-WaterSmart. For this purpose, a pilot study was operated at the municipal waste water treatment plant (WWTP) of Aquafin at Woumen as described in chapter 1.4.

1.3 Pilot tests at De Watergroep: integration of RO in drinking water treatment

In full-scale, the RO can be integrated at two locations in the treatment train of WPC De Blankaart (Figure 1). Renovation works are planned for the water production center. The scheme given is the planned situation. Currently, the treatment process includes separate sand filters and activated carbon filters instead of dual layer filters. The potential locations in the planned situation are:

- Location 1: in partial stream after the dual layer filtration;
- Location 2: in partial stream or in full stream after the dual-stage Granular Activated Carbon

(GAC) filtration.

Figure 1: Potential RO scenarios at WPC De Blankaart considering the treatment process after completion of the actual renovation.

RO pilot tests were planned at WPC De Blankaart in two phases. In the first phase, a single element RO pilot study was performed for both locations described above. This phase took place from September to December 2021 and focused on fouling. The pilot container was tested in a scenario 2 setup (after the GAC filtration). The results are discussed in chapter 2.

In the following phase, a demo scale RO pilot was operated for nine months. The RO configuration selected is a Closed Circuit RO (CCRO). The goal was to obtain a minimum of 85 % recovery, with the ambition to strive for 95 % recovery and to prove stable operation at all test conditions. The results are discussed in chapter 3.

1.3.1 Overall Goals

The main project goal is to improve the water availability of WPC De Blankaart. Therefore, the tolerance levels for chlorides need to be increased by RO technology, since the existing installation

is not capable of chloride removal. An additional benefit might be increased removal of Organic Micropollutants (OMPs). The goals of RO pilot testing at WPC De Blankaart are:

- Stable operation of the RO technology
- Validation of removal efficiency of the target components (like pesticides and pharmaceutical residues);
- Optimization of the recovery rate (water efficiency);
- Evaluation of operational deployability as a step towards full scale.

The latter two goals will be tested in a second phase with the CCRO pilot of 10 m³/h. The first two goals are partially covered by the single element RO test of the first phase.

1.3.1.1 Validation of Removal Efficiency

Reverse osmosis is the most obvious technology to be implemented as an extra treatment step in the conventional treatment train of WPC De Blankaart. This technology results in extensive removal of monovalent ions, like chloride and sodium and has the potential for the removal of nitrates and organic micropollutants.

Removal of chlorides is considered to be the main priority since chlorides cannot be removed in the conventional treatment train of WPC De Blankaart and are one of the most limiting factors for drinking water production.

The second priority is the removal of organic micropollutants (OMPs) since these also influence the water availability and the operational cost of the conventional treatment, i.e., frequent regeneration of the activated carbon filters.

Nitrate is mostly limiting the water abstraction during the winter. For nitrate, a removal efficiency of 50 – 96 % is feasible with RO (Schoeman and Steyn, 2003). However, the selected membrane type has an impact on the retention of nitrate. The results of pilot testing with a specific RO membrane will thus only be indicative.

The expected removal efficiencies of salts and nitrate can already be determined by means of simulations and will be validated with the pilot setup. As such, also the future situation with increased water quality limits for chlorides, conductivity, and nitrate can be estimated by means of simulations.

The retention of organic micropollutants can only be estimated based on literature data. The size and polarity of the OMP can have a large impact on its removal rate. With RO pilot tests, further insight into removal efficiencies can be obtained.

1.3.1.2 Optimization of Recovery

One of the largest disadvantages of RO technology is that part of the water is lost as a concentrate,

which in turn has a negative impact on water availability. Therefore, a minimum recovery of 85 % is required. RO pilot testing must confirm the feasibility of 85 % recovery or higher for a full-scale RO installation. Additionally, an estimate is needed of the related energy consumption, chemical dosing, and the composition of the concentrate stream. The choice of the RO membranes and the configuration of the RO installation can have a large impact.

1.3.1.3 Evaluation of Operational Deployability

The results of the pilot tests at the two locations will be evaluated for:

- Pressure build-up versus time
- Frequency and reversibility of membrane clogging (fouling/scaling)
- Optimal operation
 - o Cleaning cycles
 - o Chemicals consumption
 - o Type and need of pre-filtration
- The efficiency of the installation (recovery, energy,...)
- Seasonal impact

Based on the available test data, the deployability will be evaluated on a larger pilot scale:

- Comparison between the two locations and partial stream versus full stream;
- Membrane types;
- Estimation of water quality (mineral composition, hardness, OMPs, microbiological safety) and remineralization needs;
- Evaluation of operational simplicity and flexibility of the installation and possibility for discontinuous operation;
- CAPEX and OPEX estimation for the different scenarios, including costs for the disposal/treatment of the concentrate, remineralization, and operational impact downstream of the RO in the water treatment train.

1.4 Pilot tests at Aquafin: Reuse of WWTP effluent

Treated effluent of the WWTP Woumen could be used as an alternative source of intake water in the drinking water production train of De Watergroep, either by adding the effluent to the intake buffer or directly adding it into the drinking water production train. This would *de facto* result in direct water reuse.

The WWTP of Woumen is a medium-sized WWTP of 18,000 inhabitant equivalents (IE_{BOD54}), with a year-round average flow rate of 12,491 m³/d (2023) and a minimal dry weather flow of around 2500 m³/d. The geographical distance between the WWTP of Aquafin and WPC De Blankaart is 1.7 km.

A pilot installation was operated at WWTP Woumen to determine the treatment necessary to reach the required quality for use by De Watergroep. The pilot was equipped with ultrafiltration (UF), reverse osmosis (RO), activated carbon (GAC) and UV disinfection subunits.

Specific research questions addressed during this project included:

- What are the problematic parameters for achieving water reuse?

This question is addressed prior to technology selection for the pilot, since the required quality improvement decides what technologies are necessary. The problematic parameters depend on the point of entry of the treated WWTP effluent into the drinking water treatment. Since this intake point is also still open, the problematic parameters are based on the scenario of ‘minimal effluent polishing’. In this scenario, the effluent is introduced in the reservoir at the WPC, before the start of the drinking water treatment. The effluent will thus go through all treatment steps in Figure 1. The problematic parameters are addressed in Section 4.2.

The ‘minimal effluent polishing’ scenario will identify the parameters that should be reduced in any case. Any other scenario will need at least the same level of treatment. Based on the ‘minimal effluent polishing’ scenario the achievable quality and other scenarios will be evaluated.

- Which water quality can be obtained after UF, RO, GAC and UV?

This question addresses which removal efficiencies can be obtained for problematic parameters (nutrients, micropollutants, E. coli, metals, ...) and it demonstrates remaining concentrations. Mass balance flows throughout the system are investigated. Through this water quality review, we will not only learn about the quality of intake water for drinking water production, but also about the quality of waste streams that will have to be handled. The water quality results are addressed in Section 4.4.

- What is the optimal operational strategy for the pilot, in terms of operational setpoints, control mechanisms, maintenance and cleaning?

The selected technologies are mature and used widely on a full scale. However, the source of treated WWTP effluent has some specific challenges leading to operational problems that should be taken into account when scaling up this practice. The operational challenges determine for example which

water recovery can be obtained with the pilot. The operational challenges will be discussed in Section 4.5.

- How to integrate this practice in the drinking water production in WPC de Blankaart?

This question addresses issues related to full-scale implementation of WWTP effluent reuse next to water quality and operational stability. Impact of the receiving surface water and discharge of waste streams are such issues. Moreover, other scenarios than the ‘minimal effluent polishing’ scenario are possible and deserve some attention. These implications are discussed in the overall conclusions in Chapter 6.

1.5 Current state of the market

Reverse osmosis is widely used in water treatment and reuse schemes. **CCCRO or closed-circuit reverse osmosis** is an innovative alternative operational way to operate reverse osmosis that allows a very high recovery, thus very minimal water losses. The membranes used are identical to conventional reverse osmosis. The main difference is a cyclic operation of the system (semi-batch). During a short Plug Flow (PF) phase, the pressure in the system is low. Fresh feed is brought into the system and simultaneously the concentrate generated during the previous cycle is flushed away. As the pressure is low in this phase, almost no permeate stream is produced. After the PF, a closed-circuit phase (CC) starts where no concentrate leaves the system. During CC mode, the concentrate stream leaving the membranes is fully recirculated back to the inlet to mix with the fresh feedwater before entering the membranes again. The permeate produced equals the feed flow during the CC phase. Due to the recycling of concentrate, the salinity in the system increases. To maintain the permeate flow, the pressure is gradually increased to overcome osmotic pressure increase besides some other effects like concentration polarization. Figure 2 and Figure 3 show the variation of pressure and conductivity during the cyclic operation for both concentrate loop and permeate loop.

Figure 2: Typical fluctuation of pressure (above) and conductivity (below) during the closed circuit reverse osmoses operation in the concentrate loop.

Figure 3: Typical fluctuation of pressure (above) and conductivity (below) during the closed-circuit reverse osmoses operation at the permeate side.

In light of the increasing water stress, the need for sustainable solutions becomes ever more critical. One approach to address this challenge is through **treated waste water reuse**, which can serve

various applications including irrigation, flushing, industrial processes, cooling water, and even potable water (Wintgens et al., 2006).

The link between water scarcity and water reuse becomes evident when recognizing that the reuse of treated waste water for drinking water, also known as potable reuse (EPA, 2017), is a promising strategy to alleviate pressure on traditional freshwater sources. As water stress intensifies, it is crucial to exploit alternative sources, and potable reuse offers a sustainable solution. However, successfully implementing this strategy requires not only technological advancements but also a significant level of acceptance among local residents towards the reuse of recycled water (Q. Gu et al., 2015). This social aspect is essential for an effective and widely supported approach to water reuse as a sustainable solution for water scarcity.

Reverse Osmosis for waste water reuse is a mature market. Based on a report of Markets and Markets ([Waste water Reverse Osmosis Membrane Market Size, Industry Share Growth Forecast, Global Trends Report, \[Latest\] \(marketsandmarkets.com\)](https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/ResearchReports.aspx?Report=Waste+water+Reverse+Osmosis+Membrane+Market+Size,+Industry+Share+Growth+Forecast,+Global+Trends+Report,+[Latest]&MarketID=MM190200001)) the market is worth about 0.9 billion USD and will increase significantly in the coming years. Reverse Osmosis is a highly effective technology for removing a wide range of contaminants from water. Given the high water quality standards required in industrial water reuse projects, most water reuse schemes include a reverse osmosis step. Within LL Flanders no technological innovations are aspired to. The two main partners involved (Aquafin and De Watergroep) are public water companies and they will not exploit the results commercially. The pilot tests are focused specifically on the integration and application of these technologies in a drinking water production scheme.

Reuse of municipal waste water for industrial water reuse is widely applied. Few cases are known where treated municipal waste water is applied for potable reuse, most of them are not in Europe. In Flanders one reference is known (Aquaduin, Torreele). The plant is based on a treatment with ultrafiltration and reverse osmosis. The treated water is infiltrated locally in the dune area and only reused after passage through a natural barrier (indirect potable reuse or IPR). Within the project B-WaterSmart, the ambition is to reuse the water directly without a natural barrier (direct potable reuse or DPR). In Europe no references are known for DPR. Worldwide fewer than 5 large DPR references exist (Jeffrey P. et al., 2022).

Most DPR treatment schemes include the use of RO, except for Windhoek (Namibia). In general, the technologies applied are readily available and at TRL 9 for example for surface water. This is also the case for the technologies selected in this case study (see Chapter 4). However, WWTP effluent has specific challenges and its quality varies between continents and countries depending on local legislation and on how the waste water treatment sector is organized. Figure 4 shows some examples of technologies used in specific DPR cases. The reuse schemes are highly variable. It is therefore necessary to assess region-specific challenges to combine suitable technologies.

Figure 4: Applied technologies in DPR plants (Figure adapted from Aleksić & Šušteršič (2022))

2 Pilot study De Watergroep: Treatment of off spec raw water phase 1, single-element RO pilot

2.1.1 Specific goals RO Pilot Phase 1

During the market study, a piloting strategy was developed. It was decided to rent first a small-scale pilot to get familiar with RO technology prior to installing a demo scale and more complex RO pilot. With the small-scale pilot, a first element test was conducted to investigate fouling. Fouling typically occurs in the front end of an RO system and results in a higher pressure drop across the RO system and a lower permeate flow. Insight into the fouling behavior can help anticipating problems in the following RO pilot phase.

The goals of the first RO pilot are, thus:

- to evaluate the potential for membrane fouling;
- to obtain first insight into the suitability of the RO location (i.e., scenario 1 versus 2 - Figure 1);
- to optimize chemical consumption and cleaning regimes related to fouling;
- to gain valuable insight into RO membrane technology and operation.

2.2 Pilot Description phase 1

2.2.1 Location and Timing

For the RO pilot test phase 1 a testing period of 3 months was planned. The testing took place from 16/09/2021 till 17/12/2021. Originally, it was planned to test both the effluent from the sand filtration and from the granular activated carbon filters (GAC). The test started on 16/09/2021 on the water from the activated carbon filters, with the intention of switching later to the water from the sand filtration. Due to the lower Non Purgeable Organic Carbon (NPOC) level in the effluent of the activated carbon filters, i.e., < 3 mg/l NPOC, it was expected to be the location with the lowest fouling potential and thus the most smooth operation to start with. However, during the test, it was decided to remain the full three months in the same location since an unexpected fouling behavior was detected.

2.2.2 Pilot Configuration

The pilot container was a rental unit containing both an UF and RO unit. Only the RO configuration, as shown in Figure 5, was used for the pilot test. Water from the activated carbon filters was taken from the outlet collector pipe, combining the effluent of all 6 activated carbon filters from the full-scale drinking water plant, and was fed gravitationally to the RO pilot container.

Figure 5: Schematic representation of the pilot configuration.

The RO pilot was equipped with a feed tank, a cartridge filter of 10 µm, a high-pressure supply pump, an 8" RO membrane housed in a pressure vessel, and a manual valve for controlling the recovery. Also, a coarse scraper (not shown in Figure 5) was present in the feed inlet line prior to the in-line measurements.

Antiscalant was dosed upstream the cartridge filter. The high-pressure pump was provided with a variable frequency drive to control the flow rate to the RO membrane at 2.5 m³/h. The permeate and concentrate were returned to the reservoir via the ring channel.

2.2.2.1 Membrane Characteristics

One new membrane was used throughout the testing. The membrane selected was the membrane considered based on simulation software in the feasibility study (VITO/De Watergroep, June 2020) and is manufactured by DuPont.

The membrane characteristics are listed below:

- Model No.: FilmTec™ BW30XFRLE-400/34
- Material: polyamide, thin-film composite
- Active filter area: 37 m²
- Max. operating pressure: 41 bar
- Minimum salt rejection: 99.1 %
- Module size: 8"

2.2.2.2 Antiscalant

The antiscalant Hypersperse MDC714 from Suez was supplied together with the rental pilot container. This phosphonate-based antiscalant was diluted with permeate (dilution ratio 1:25) in the

antiscalant storage tank of 60 liters and dosed at a dosing rate of 2.2 ppm. At a constant feed flow rate of 2.5 m³/h to the RO membrane, this corresponded to a pure antiscalant consumption of 132 ml/d.. The antiscalant had to be refilled biweekly on average.

Note that for the demo scale RO pilot (10 m³/h), which will run for a longer period, a non-phosphonate based antiscalant is preferred. Both permeate and concentrate are collected and sent back to the reservoir. As such, antiscalant is ending up in the reservoir, which is already facing algae blooms in summer.

2.2.2.3 Online Measurements

The pilot container is provided with online logging of the following parameters:

- Temperature feed water (°C);
- Turbidity of feed water (NTU);
- Level buffer tank (m);
- Conductivity feed water (µS/cm);
- Feed flow rate (m³/h);
- Permeate flow rate (m³/h);
- Feed pump pressure (mwc);
- Concentrate pressure (mwc);
- Conductivity of permeate (µS/cm);
- Frequency of feed pump (Hz);
- Pressure drop along RO element (mwc) – calculated value;

2.2.3 Operation

The pilot was started up on September 16th at 2:21 pm with a new dry RO membrane on the effluent of the activated carbon filters. The concentrate valve was further opened during the afternoon at 3:48 pm to decrease the permeate flow to the minimum possible with this pilot container setup. The goal was to approach as close as possible to the design recovery flow (12-15%) of one RO element, as per membrane suppliers recommendations. However, this was not possible with this setup, even with the concentrate valve fully opened, since there was no throttling valve in the permeate line. Moreover, the feed pump flow was insufficient, causing a low cross flow velocity in the element and a low pressure drop. A valve in the permeate line would provide more backpressure which could have helped balancing the flows towards the recommended recovery. Instead, the operation was set at +/- 30% recovery, which is beyond the recommended operational limits.

2.2.3.1 First Element Simulation

At the start of the pilot test, a first element simulation was done with the DuPont's software WAVE based on the average water quality from 2016 to 2020 in the outlet of the activated carbon filters. A water temperature of 19°C was considered, which was the actual water temperature around the time of start-up. A flow factor of 1 was selected since a new membrane was used. Figure 6 gives an overview of the main operational parameters.

Pass		Pass 1
Stream Name		Stream 1
Water Type		Surface Water (SDI < 5)
Number of Elements		1
Total Active Area	(m ²)	37.2
Feed Flow per Pass	(m ³ /h)	2.50
Feed TDS	(mg/L)	768.3
Feed Pressure	(bar)	5.3
Flow Factor Per Stage		1.00
Permeate Flow per Pass	(m ³ /h)	0.82
Pass Average flux	(LMH)	22.2
Permeate TDS	(mg/L)	14.43
Pass Recovery		32.8 %
Average NDP	(bar)	4.5
Specific Energy	(kWh/m ³)	0.56
Temperature	(°C)	19.0
pH		7.1
Chemical Dose		-
RO System Recovery		33.0 %
Net RO System Recovery		33.0%

Figure 6: RO system overview from first element simulation at start-up of the pilot test.

The suboptimal flow conditions were taken into account in this simulation, resulting in the following design warning of the software:

RO Design Warnings

Design Warning	Limit	Value	Pass	Stage	Element	Product
Concentrate Flow Rate < Minimum Limit (m ³ /h)	3.41	1.67	1	1	1	BW30XFRLE-400/34
Element Recovery > Maximum Limit (%)	15.0	33.0	1	1	1	BW30XFRLE-400/34

The concentration of the fouling materials at the membrane surface increases with increasing permeate flux, i.e., the permeate flow rate per unit membrane area, and increasing element recovery, i.e., the ratio of permeate flow rate to feed flow rate for a single element. The effective osmotic pressure at the membrane surface will be higher due to concentration polarization, caused by the higher permeate flow through the membrane leaving a higher concentrated stream behind in the RO element channel. Also, the low cross-flow velocity will amplify this effect. Therefore, a system with a high permeate flux like the pilot setup is likely to experience higher fouling rates. The expectation is thus that fouling will occur faster than if the pilot is operated within the optimal design boundaries.

2.2.3.2 Normalization

The performance of an RO system is influenced by the feedwater composition, feed pressure, temperature, and recovery. In order to distinguish between such normal phenomena and performance changes due to fouling or problems, the measured permeate flow and salt passage have to be normalized. Normalization is a comparison of the actual performance to a given reference performance while the influences of operating parameters are taken into account. For this pilot test, normalization with reference to the initial measured system performance was chosen.

As per FilmTec™ Reverse Osmosis Membranes Technical Manual, the time for a dry RO membrane to reach stabilized performance can be some hours or a few days of operation. Dry membranes tend to start at a slightly higher flow, and the salt rejection, in general, improves during the first few hours or days of operation before stabilizing. Based on this, the initial system performance point selected was 7:40 am on September 17th since a clear jump (Figure 7) was visible from 0.33% to 0.28% for the salt passage since start-up, indicating an improved salt rejection.

Figure 7: Salt passage (%) evaluation to determine initial system performance point.

The calculation of the normalized data is based on:

- Formulas from Chapter 7, The Guidebook to Membrane Desalination Technology (Wilf M, 2007) unless stated otherwise;
- Permeate pressure is calculated based on the height of permeate line (2.25 m);
- Average osmotic pressure is calculated for a concentration of the feed-concentrate $C_{fc} < 20,000$ mg/l based on Chapter 5, FilmTec™ Reverse Osmosis Membranes Technical Manual (2023) ([FilmTec Reverse Osmosis/Nanofiltration Membranes Technical Manual \(dupont.com\)](https://www.dupont.com)). The temperature correction factor TCF is based on equation 74 (for temperatures $< 25^{\circ}\text{C}$) from this chapter.
- The osmotic pressure of the permeate has been ignored since assumed to be negligible;
- Factor of 0.69 for calculating feed TDS based on feed conductivity measured; this averaged factor was calculated based on the cation and anion composition from the water analysis data from the past 5 years.
- Factor of 0.55 for calculating permeate TDS based on permeate conductivity measured.

2.3 Results

2.3.1 On-Line Measurements and Performance Trending

2.3.1.1 Period from stable operation till CIP

The first operational period discussed is from the initial system performance point (7:40 am on September 17th) till the CIP on November 18th. In that period, two events were logged:

1. Pilot manually stopped from Friday 24/09 until Monday 04/10 in the morning due to an empty antiscalant drum and delayed supply of fresh antiscalant.
2. Power outage on Friday 22/10 noon; remote restart of pilot operation on Saturday 23/10 in the morning.

Both events are indicated in Figure 8 to Figure 12. In the graphs, the actual period of these events is left out.

For the first event, it was not fully clear how long the RO pilot was operated without antiscalant. It is possible that there was no or reduced antiscalant dosing on the day before the pilot was stopped. It is also unclear if this explains the sudden increase in permeate flow and flux shortly before the shutdown (Figure 9 and Figure 12).

During the shutdown period, the RO membrane was kept wet without adding conservation chemicals. The pilot was restarted after a week. Meanwhile, the feed water temperature had dropped with 4°C. A reduction in the feed water temperature resulted in a reduction in permeate flow (Figure 9). Since there was a corresponding increase in feed pressure (Figure 10), the normalized permeate flow was not impacted.

The second event was very short and had no related impact.

Figure 8: Salt passage and water temperature for the period from stable operation till CIP.

Figure 9: Permeate flow and water temperature for the period from stable operation till CIP.

Figure 10: Feed pressure and net driving pressure for the period from stable operation till CIP.

Figure 11: Difference in the normalized salt passage (NSP) and normalized permeate flow (NPF) compared to initial system performance point for the period from stable operation till CIP.

Figure 12: Specific flux, flux, and temperature for the period from stable operation till CIP.

In Chapter 6 of FilmTec™ Reverse Osmosis Membranes Technical Manual, cleaning of the RO membrane is recommended if:

- the normalized salt passage has increased by 5 – 10%;
- or, if the normalized permeate flow has decreased by 10%;
- or, if the normalized pressure drop (feed pressure minus concentrate pressure) has increased by 10 – 15%.

The normalized salt passage had increased by 10% by mid-October and remained stable until the end of October (Figure 11). At that point, it was already clear that a CIP would be needed soon. By mid-November, the normalized salt passage had increased by 15% compared to the initial system performance point.

The normalized permeate flow decreased only very gradually in the beginning (Figure 9); the same trend applies to the permeability, i.e. the specific flux (Figure 12). This decrease accelerated in the last week of October, reaching a 10% decrease by mid-November. At that point, cleaning in place (CIP) was performed.

The normalized pressure drop ranged from 0.1 to 0.2 bar but was difficult to interpret. Since this value was calculated based on feed and concentrate pressure, which are in a higher range (> 4 bar), the pressure sensors might not have had sufficient accuracy.

2.3.1.2 CIP

On Thursday, November 18th, the CIP cleaning was performed in the following order:

1. Alkaline CIP with NaOH
2. Rinsing with permeate
3. Acid CIP with citric acid
4. Rinsing with permeate

For both the CIP liquid and the rinsing, permeate was collected in an external vessel prior to the start of the CIP. For the CIP liquid preparation, the permeate was heated and then pumped to the feed tank of the pilot container. An additional pump was used to circulate the heated permeate over the feed tank while NaOH or citric acid was dosed to prepare the CIP solution. Then the CIP solution was pumped into the RO pressure vessel with the high-pressure pump at 2.5 m³/h. Both permeate and concentrate were recycled back into the feed tank, while the pH of the CIP solution was monitored with the multimeter. During the acid CIP, additional citric acid dosing was required since the pH increased fast to 3.2.

Table 1: Overview of process conditions during CIP.

	NaOH CIP	Citric Acid CIP
Start Temperature (°C)	27	32
End Temperature (°C)	18	29
Start pH	12.25	2.95
End pH	12.17	2.88
Start conductivity (µs/cm)	4700	848
End Conductivity (µs/cm)	4660	1010
CIP recirculation duration	3 hours	1 hour
Rinsing duration	1 hour	20 minutes
Rinsing temperature (°C)	12 – 14 °C	12 – 15 °C

Regarding the CIP procedure,

- No soaking was done, since the extent of the fouling was not known;
- CIP recirculation flow rate was equal to the feed flow rate during RO operation, i.e., 2.5 m³/h due to the capacity of the high-pressure pump. According to FilmTec™ Reverse Osmosis Membranes Technical Manual a flow of 3 – 5 m³/h is recommended during the CIP recirculation prior to soaking. A flow rate of 6 – 10 m³/h is recommended after the soaking of the membrane.
- Also, the recommended flushing temperature of 20°C was not met.
- The CIP was executed in manual mode. However, due to an error in the automation, the antiscalant pump was still on during the CIP.

2.3.1.3 Period after CIP

The second operational period, from CIP until the stop of pilot operation on December 17th, is discussed and compared with the initial system performance point (7:40 am on September 17th). After the CIP, i.e., event 3, two other events were logged in the second operational period:

4. Power outage on Monday 22/11 around 6 pm; manual restart of pilot operation on Wednesday 24/11 in the afternoon.
5. Antiscalant dosing was intentionally stopped.

All events are indicated in Figure 13 to Figure 17. For events 3 and 4, the actual duration period of these events is left out in the graphs.

The normalized salt passage did not improve by the cleaning of the membrane. At first, it seemed that the normalized salt passage had stabilized, but then a rapid increase in the normalized salt passage took place (Figure 13).

The normalized permeate flow was lower than before the cleaning of the membrane (Figure 14). In the week after the CIP, the normalized permeate flow seemed to improve. However, this improvement was temporary, and shortly after, the normalized permeate flow decreased more rapidly compared to before the CIP. The feed pressure and the net driving pressure increased rapidly (Figure 15) due to the fast drop in water temperature (5 °C).

Flux and specific flux were also not restored after the CIP (Figure 17). Instead, flux and specific flux were lower and decreased further. It is clear that the CIP did not have the expected result. Therefore, it was decided to perform a membrane autopsy at the pilot stop.

The 5th event, an intentional stop of antiscalant dosing was chosen for the last week of operation, to see if it could help to explain the trend seen at the first event, when there was the suspicion of no or limited antiscalant dosing (see section 2.3.1.1). At first, the stop of the antiscalant dosing seemed to have a stabilizing effect since the normalized permeate flow no longer decreased. However, shortly after, the water temperature increased by about 2°C. The decrease in the feed and net driving pressure (Figure 15) is clearly visible and can directly be linked to the water temperature trend in

timing. Most likely the stop of antiscalant dosing for a short time did not have an effect. The combination of increased water temperature and lower feed pressure, however, did only have a stabilizing effect but did not improve permeate flow.

Figure 13: Salt passage and water temperature for the period after CIP. The fluctuation of the salt passage at the end of the test period is due to inaccuracy of the conductivity measurement.

Figure 14: Permeate flow and water temperature for the period after CIP.

Figure 15: Feed pressure and net driving pressure for the period after CIP.

Figure 16: Difference in normalized salt passage (NSP) and normalized permeate flow (NPF) compared to initial system performance point and water temperature for the period after CIP. The fluctuation of the salt passage at the end of the test period is due to inaccuracy of the conductivity measurement.

Figure 17: Specific flux, flux and temperature for the period after CIP.

2.3.2 Lab Results

2.3.2.1 Period from stable operation till CIP

A summary of the averaged lab results for the feed stream, i.e., effluent from the GAC filters, the permeate, the concentrate and the removal rate for the test period prior to the CIP are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Overview of the average water composition for the feed, permeate and concentrate and average removal rate in the test period prior to the CIP.

Parameter	Unit	Feed	Permeate	Concentrate	Removal (%)
Al	µg/l	4	1	6	84.9 %
As	µg/l	0.3	0	0.4	100 %
B	µg/l	112.2	82.3	127.2	26.4 %
Ba	µg/l	33	0	45	99.7 %
Ca	mg/l	95.3	0.4	135.8	99.6 %
Cl	mg/l	190	9.7	258	94.8 %
F	mg/l	0.2	0	0.3	95.8 %
Fe	µg/l	6	3	33	75.8 %
K	mg/l	41.9	1.3	59.0	97.0 %
Mg	mg/l	16.7	0	23.5	99.8 %
Mn	µg/l	1	0	2	100 %
Na	mg/l	136.3	4.8	192.4	96.5 %
PO ₄	mg/l	0.01	0.01	1.35	28.2 %
	PO ₄				
SiO ₂	mg/l	9.8	0.3	14.1	97.3 %
SO ₄	mg/l	209	4.3	294	97.9 %
Sr	µg/l	404	1	564	99.7 %
TDS	mg/l	799	29	1189	96.4 %
NPOC	mg/l	2.2	0.2	3.3	92.1 %

Parameter	Unit	Feed	Permeate	Concentrate	Removal (%)
pH	-	7.16	5.35	7.26	-

The lab results of the feed water quality from just before the CIP, i.e. lab data from 18/11/2021, were used for a first element simulation with the software WAVE. For NH_4^+ and NO_3^- data from the 16th of November was used. For bromide, the average value of the water quality from 2016 to 2020 was used. Note that the feed water TDS (Figure 18) are calculated by WAVE based on the ion composition and are higher than the TDS measured from the sample, i.e. 799.4 mg/l.

Also, the actual recovery and feed pressure from the pilot were used as input for the simulation (Figure 18). A flow factor of 0.91 was used to approach the feed pressure from the pilot.

Pass		Pass 1
Stream Name		Stream 1
Water Type		Surface Water (SDI < 5)
Number of Elements		1
Total Active Area	(m ²)	37.2
Feed Flow per Pass	(m ³ /h)	2.50
Feed TDS	(mg/L)	901.9
Feed Pressure	(bar)	6.1
Flow Factor Per Stage		0.92
Permeate Flow per Pass	(m ³ /h)	0.67
Pass Average flux	(LMH)	18.2
Permeate TDS	(mg/L)	12.07
Pass Recovery		26.8 %
Average NDP	(bar)	5.1
Specific Energy	(kWh/m ³)	0.79
Temperature	(°C)	13.3
pH		7.2
Chemical Dose		-
RO System Recovery		27.0 %
Net RO System Recovery		27.0%

Figure 18: RO system overview from first element simulation prior to CIP.

The simulated permeate and concentrate quality are shown in Table 3. These results are compared with the actual measured quality on 18/11. Considering the fact that the RO element was operated outside the recommended specifications, the membrane was most likely exposed to high concentration polarization and other phenomena which lie outside the design boundaries for the modelling software. Nevertheless, the lab results still match quite well with the theoretical values. Note that the phosphate level measured in the concentrate is significantly higher than the simulated value. This is due to the antiscalant dosed, which ends up in the concentrate.

Table 3: Simulated results from first element simulation prior to CIP versus lab results.

Parameter	Unit	Input simulation		Simulated		Measured	
		Feed	Permeate	Concentrate	Permeate	Concentrate	
B	µg/l	100	40	120	77.4	125.1	
Br	mg/l	0.15	0	0.2	-	-	
Ba	µg/l	30	0	40	0	45	
Ca	mg/l	94.8	0.53	129.7	0.1	140.9	
Cl	mg/l	174.6	1.75	238.5	8	258	
F	mg/l	0.19	0	0.25	0	0.3	
K	mg/l	41.9	0.81	57.1	0.9	59.6	
Mg	mg/l	16.1	0.09	22.02	0	23.1	
Na	mg/l	132	2.28	180	3.8	187.9	
NH ₄	mg/l	0.02	0	0.03	-	-	
NO ₃	mg/l	11.2	0.52	15.16	-	-	
PO ₄	mg/l	0.01	0	0.01	0	1.91	
	PO ₄						
SiO ₂	mg/l	9.06	0.04	12.39	0	14	
SO ₄	mg/l	194.2	0.81	265.7	5	282	
Sr	µg/l	390	0	530	0	558	
HCO ₃	mg/l	226.3	4.97	307.9	-	-	

		Input simulation	Simulated		Measured	
CO ₃	mg/l	0.29	0	0.57	-	-
CO ₂	mg/l	20.68	20.43	20.86	-	-
TDS	mg/l	901.8	12.07	1,231	23.4	1,165
Conductivity	µs/cm	1,417	18	1,901	27.2	1,721
pH	-	7.2	5.7	7.3	5.34	7.39

2.3.2.2 CIP

The spent CIP solution from both the alkaline and acid CIP was analyzed in the lab. In Table 4 the composition of the CIP solutions, as well as total amount of components removed, is shown. The total amount removed is calculated based on an estimated CIP solution volume. The volume in the CIP system, i.e., pressure vessel, pipes, and feed tank, was estimated to be 490 liters.

Alkaline CIP with NaOH is useful in the removal of organic foulants of natural origin, polymerized silica scale, and biological material (fungi, mold, slimes and biofilm). NPOC is clearly being removed with this CIP based on the removed mass from Table 4. Also, part of the inorganic deposits was removed. Note that the high sodium level of this CIP liquid is to be attributed to the NaOH used for preparing the CIP liquid. The same remark applies to the NPOC level of the acid CIP liquid, which is attributed to the citric acid used for preparing the CIP liquid.

Acid CIP with citric acid is typically useful in removing inorganic scale (e.g. calcium carbonate, calcium sulfate, barium sulfate, strontium sulfate) and metal oxides/hydroxides (e.g. iron, manganese, aluminum, ...) and inorganic-based colloidal material. In Table 4, the amount of iron and manganese removed is clearly high. Also, the amount of removed inorganic scale seems to indicate that the CIP was successful for this type of scaling.

In general, the CIP performed seemed to be quite effective based on the lab results. Unfortunately, the performance trending after CIP does not confirm the expected success of the CIP.

Note the high phosphate levels in both the alkaline and acid CIP liquid. This can be attributed to the active antiscalant dosing pump throughout the whole CIP procedure, as mentioned in section 2.3.1.2. Nevertheless, the amount of phosphate in the acid CIP liquid is significantly higher than for the alkaline CIP liquid, despite the shorter duration of the acid CIP. Most likely, the continuous dosing of the antiscalant in the recirculated CIP was building up a layer of phosphate scaling in combination with the high pH, which was then released by the acid CIP.

Table 4: Composition of spent alkaline and acid CIP liquid.

Parameter	NaOH CIP	Citric Acid CIP	Unit	NaOH CIP mass	Citric Acid CIP mass	Unit
Al	22	137	µg/l	10.85	67.58	mg
As	1	5.1	µg/l	0.49	2.52	mg
B	79.8	98.2	µg/l	39.37	48.44	mg
Ba	7	68	µg/l	3.45	33.55	mg
Ca	37.1	70.1	mg/l	18.30	34.58	g
Cl	97	81	mg/l	47.85	39.96	g
F	1.2	0	mg/l	0.59	0.00	g
Fe	95	9559	µg/l	46.87	4715.62	mg
K	22.6	18.2	mg/l	11.15	8.98	g
Mg	0.4	13.7	mg/l	0.20	6.76	g
Mn	12	690	µg/l	5.92	340.39	mg
Na	618.8	80.5	mg/l	305.26	39.71	g
PO ₄	10.55	151.1	mg/l PO ₄	5.20	74.54	g PO ₄
SiO ₂	5.5	5.6	mg/l	2.71	2.76	g
SO ₄	84	89	mg/l	41.44	43.91	g
Sr	137	303	µg/l	67.58	149.48	mg
NPOC	40.1	-(1)	mg/l	-(1)	-(1)	g

(1) NPOC values in citric acid CIP not reported as the citric acid contributes itself to the NPOC value.

2.3.2.3 Period after CIP

A summary of the averaged lab results for the feed stream, i.e., effluent from the GAC filters, the permeate, the concentrate and the removal rate for the test period after the CIP are shown in Table 5. The TDS removal rate (94.6%) is slightly lower than prior to the CIP (96.4%). However, it cannot be considered a significant difference.

Table 5: Overview of average water composition for the feed, permeate and concentrate and average removal rate in the test period after the CIP.

Parameter	Unit	Feed	Permeate	Concentrate	Removal (%)
Al	µg/l	8	2	11	63.0 %
As	µg/l	0.7	0	0.8	100 %
B	µg/l	104.5	69.1	117.7	33.8 %
Ba	µg/l	32	0	42	100 %
Ca	mg/l	102.7	0.1	141.1	99.9 %
Cl	mg/l	176	5.0	218	97.2 %
F	mg/l	0.2	0	0.3	100 %
Fe	µg/l	4	1	6	80.3 %
K	mg/l	37.6	0.7	50.6	98.2 %
Mg	mg/l	16.5	0	22.2	100 %
Mn	µg/l	2	0	4	100 %
Na	mg/l	129.1	3.2	170.9	97.5 %
PO ₄	mg/l	0.03	0.00	1.20	90.0 %
	PO ₄				
SiO ₂	mg/l	10.2	0.2	13.7	98.2 %
SO ₄	mg/l	208	1.8	265	99.1 %
Sr	µg/l	406	0.4	533	99.9 %
TDS	mg/l	816	44	1107	94.6 %
NPOC	mg/l	1.9	0.2	2.5	86.4 %
pH	-	7.31	5.48	7.42	-

2.3.3 SDI Measurements

Silt is composed of suspended particulates of all types that can accumulate on the membrane surface.

Sources of silt are organic colloids, iron corrosion products, precipitated iron hydroxide, algae, and fine particular matter. Silt Density Index (SDI) testing is a widely accepted method for estimating the rate at which colloidal and particle fouling will occur on RO membranes. SDI is a measurement of the fouling potential of suspended solids, whereas turbidity is a measurement of the amount of suspended solids.

2.3.3.1 Method

During the pilot test, the SDI₁₅ was measured at the outlet of both the sand filters and the activated carbon filters to make a high-level comparison between both scenarios. The Millipore SDI Tester was used with 47 mm diameter filters of 0.45 micron. Since the available pressure at the outlet of both locations was too low, a pump was used in combination with the pressure regulator of the Millipore SDI Tester to ensure a start pressure of 2.0 – 2.2 bar.

2.3.3.2 Results

The SDI results are shown in Table 6. The guideline for the feed water of an RO system is to maintain the SDI₁₅ at ≤5. To minimize the fouling, however, SDI₁₅ at <3 is recommended. The water in the outlet of the GAC filters is thus meeting the guideline of SDI₁₅ at ≤5, but is not meeting the recommendation of SDI₁₅ at <3. The water in the outlet of the sand filters exceeds both the guideline and the recommendation value.

SDI₁₅ in the range of 3 – 5 indicates that particular fouling is likely a problem and results in frequent cleaning. SDI₁₅ above 5 is considered to be unacceptable for RO membrane suppliers, and often an additional pre-treatment is recommended in this case.

Table 6: Overview of SDI15 results during test period.

	Outlet sand filters	Outlet GAC filters
Median	5.2	4.3
Average	5.2	4.3
10% percentile	4.4	3.4
90% percentile	5.9	4.8

Note that the current water quality is a worst case and that the effluent of the current activated carbon filters is of drinking water quality. Once the new post-treatment is started up, the GAC filters will be replaced by dual GAC filters. This might result in better water quality. Additionally, the sand filters will be replaced by dual media filters in the new pre-treatment. A limited number (3) of SDI₁₅ measurements were done on the effluent of the dual media filtration pilot during October and

November. The median SDI₁₅ was 4.4. This indicates that there is a potential improvement with the future dual media filtration.

2.3.4 Membrane Autopsy

Since the CIP did not have the expected result, it was decided to send the membrane for autopsy at the pilot stop. The RO pilot was stopped on Friday December 17th and the membrane was removed (Figure 19). Black particles were visible around the outer edges as well as a black deposition inside the spiral wound membrane (Figure 20).

The 10 µm cartridge filter in the suction of the high-pressure pump was also removed for visual inspection and cut open (Figure 21). A similar black deposition was found inside the cartridge filter. Note that the cartridge filter was not checked prior to the start of the pilot test. The cartridge filter was used for a couple of hours a day for 3 months at a prior location on pond water after an ultrafiltration step. Part of the fouling inside the cartridge filter could be due to this earlier location, though the UF step makes it less likely.

The autopsy of the membrane consisted of:

- Dye test;
- Fujiwara test;
- Determination of organic material;
- Determination of inorganic depositions;
- Testing of cleaning solutions.

Figure 19: RO membrane at the end of the pilot test.

Figure 20: Collection of samples from the RO membrane for the autopsy tests.

Figure 21: Top view of cartridge filter (left) and opened cartridge filter (right).

2.3.4.1 Dye Test

A dye test was performed to detect any physical defects or deterioration of the membrane surface. Areas of damage would typically show the dye to soak through the permeate side of the membrane. For the RO membrane of the pilot test, there was no dye soaking through the membrane. Therefore, the RO membrane was not damaged.

2.3.4.2 Fujiwara Test

One of the particular challenges with spiral wound RO membranes is that they are susceptible to oxidative damage. Two potential causes linked to the operation of WPC De Blankaart and the operation of the pilot were identified:

- Hypochlorite oxidation: hypochlorite is dosed prior to the sand filtration. Even though it was expected to be considerably to fully removed by the GAC filters and checked sporadically with a manual free chlorine measurement, it was not fully excluded that no residual level was present at some moments.
- Oxygen damage: RO membranes are susceptible to damage by oxygen if they are left outside operation for long periods. Generally, if a membrane plant is going to be down for over a week or two, then the system should be flushed with permeate and then preserved with sodium metabisulphite to scavenge any atmospheric oxygen. Since the RO pilot was down for 10 days and the RO membrane was not flushed or preserved, this could have been an issue.

The Fujiwara test is a qualitative colorimetric test and is indicative of oxidative damage. The test was

performed, and there was no colour indication. The test was thus negative; therefore, there was no demonstrable damage due to oxidation.

2.3.4.3 Determination of Organic and Inorganic Depositions

The dry residue and the ash content (i.e., inorganic fraction) of the foulant collected from the membrane sheet were determined (Figure 22):

- Percentage dry residue: 4.3 %
- Ash content (of the dry residue): 11 %

Figure 22: Collected foulant before drying (left), collected foulant after drying at 100°C (middle), and collected foulant after 550°C (right).

Next, the composition of the acid-soluble fraction from the ash content was determined (Table 7). These findings, i.e., the prominent presence of phosphate and iron, are in line with the data obtained from the lab analysis of the acid CIP liquid (Table 7). The remaining fraction of 6.6% of ash content was not soluble in acid.

Note that the total percentage determined is lower than 100%. This is partly attributed due to the volatilization of HCO_3 and CO_3 to CO_2 during the measurement method. Also, chlorides cannot be determined since the analytical method uses HCl.

In Figure 23, the composition of the membrane foulants is shown. The organic fraction of the foulants amounts to 89% of the dry residue.

Table 7: Overview of concentrations of inorganic depositions.

	Unit	Concentration
Sodium	in % Na	2.8
Potassium	in % K	< 1
Ammonium	in % NH ₄	< 1
Ca-hardness	in % Ca	13
Mg-hardness	in % Mg	1.2
Ortho-phosphate	in % PO ₄	36
Sulphate	in % SO ₄	4.8
Carbonate	in % CO ₃	< 1
Iron	in % Fe	9.7
Aluminum	in % Al	< 1
Non soluble	%	6.6

Figure 23: Membrane foulants composition.

2.3.4.4 Testing of Cleaning Solutions

The following cleaning solutions were tested on samples of the fouled RO membrane:

- 5% AQUATREAT Neutralcal, i.e. a NaOH based cleaner;
- 5% AQUATREAT 841, i.e. a citric acid based cleaner;
- 5% AQUATREAT 858, i.e., an alkaline cleaner with organic chelating agents, at room temperature;
- 5% AQUATREAT 858 at 37°C.

The tested cleaning solutions had very little visual cleaning effect on the membrane (Figure 24). The cleaning with 5% Aquatreat combined with Neutralcal appeared slightly better than the other cleaning solutions, but even then the cleaning is not effective. This confirms the results of the CIP performed during the RO pilot test (section 2.3.1.2).

Figure 24: RO membrane samples tested with different cleaning solutions.

2.4 Discussion of actual full scale pretreatment

During summer, WPC De Blankaart operates at half or less of the designed water production capacity. As a consequence, not all treatment steps are used at full capacity due to design limits and operational efficiency:

- 2 decanters, 1 is operational;
- 6 sand filters, 3 are operational (ZF4, ZF5, ZF6);
- 6 GAC filters, 3 are operational (AKF1, AKF2 and AKF6).

Depending on the water availability, the water production is gradually increased at the end of summer. At that point, a gradual increase in the capacity of the treatment steps is needed. The pilot test period coincided with this increase in capacity:

- the 2nd decanter was put into operation in the last week of September;
- 2 sand filters (ZF2 and ZF3) and 1 GAC filter (AKF4) were also put into operation in the last week of September;
- 1 GAC filter (AKF3) was put into operation in the 3rd week of October;
- the 6th sand filter (ZF1) and the 6th GAC filter (AKF5) were taken into operation in the first week of November.

All of these treatment steps were upstream of the RO pilot, but the effects could be detected downstream. The start-up of the 2nd decanter was detected via the SDI₁₅ measurements. The SDI₁₅ measured improved slightly as from 4/10/2021 (Table 8) and also the colour of the filters was impacted positively (Figure 25).

Table 8: Overview of SDI15 results prior to and after the start of the second decanter.

	Outlet sand filters	Outlet GAC filters
14/09/2021	5.8	5.0
24/09/2021	5.9	4.6
27/09/2021	6.2	4.6
30/09/2021	5.6	4.3
04/10/2021	4.9	4.3
06/10/2021	4.2	4.3

Figure 25: Filters from SDI15 measurement from 24/09 and 06/10. The top pictures are SDI15 filters with water from sand filtration, bottom pictures are SDI15 filters with water from GAC filtration.

The pilot container was equipped with an online turbidity measurement. The turbidity measured was typically < 0.3 NTU, which was confirmed by the analyzed samples. In the 3rd week of October, the turbidity measured by the online measurement increased suddenly and increased even further in the last week of October (Figure 26). The analyzed samples showed, however, that the turbidity of the water from the GAC filters had not increased. At that point, the sudden increase was thus attributed to the calibration need of the sensor. However, the CIP of November 18th (event 3) rinsed the sensor clean and the turbidity measurement was restored.

The observed turbidity increase could be linked to washout of activated carbon fines. The GAC filter AKF3 was started in the third week of October. After this start-up, a washout of activated carbon was detected at the sampling points. This event coincided with the increase of turbidity measured by the online NTU measurement of the pilot container. Most likely, the smaller peaks in turbidity from Figure 26 are also due to washout of carbon fines from the other GAC filters. However, the washout from AKF3 is more severe and caused fouling of the turbidity sensor.

Figure 26: Turbidity of the feed water, i.e., effluent from the GAC filtration. At event 3 the sensor was recalibrated.

Based on this information and the membrane autopsy, the irreversible fouling was very likely caused by activated carbon fines. The CIP could possibly have engraved the effect and pushed the activated carbon dust further into the membrane. Also, the washout of activated carbon fines is not limited to one event and one filter only. During an SDI measurement on February 16th 2022, carbon fines were collected on the SDI filter (Figure 27). Most likely, the fine dust is gradually released after the backwash of a filter.

Figure 27: SDI filter during carbon fines washout from GAC filtration on February 16th, 2022.

2.5 Conclusions

During the first RO pilot phase only one location was tested, i.e. downstream of the GAC filtration. At the start, this was assumed to be the more beneficial location in terms of water quality and fouling risk based on historical water quality data and SDI measurements. The membrane autopsy, gave indications for the risk of irreversible fouling by the carbon fines from the GAC filtration. At the moment, it is assumed that the carbon fines can pass a 5 micron and possibly also a 1 micron cartridge filter, thus fouling the RO membranes if located downstream. Further investigation could be done on the minimum particle size, as well as on determining a feasible technical solution for retaining the carbon fines, in order to consider this location for the next pilot phase or even for full-scale. However, it is more recommended to consider the GAC filtration as a polishing step after an RO instead of seeing the RO as the polishing step of the GAC filtration. For the next phase, it is recommended to start the demo-scale RO pilot downstream of the sand filtration and thus upstream of the GAC filtration.

The membrane autopsy showed that the fouling consisted of 89% out of organics. It was not determined that the majority of these organics were carbon fines. LC-OCD analysis could be considered during the next pilot phase, especially since the NPOC level after sand filtration is higher than after GAC filtration.

3 Pilot study De Watergroep: Treatment of off spec raw water phase 2, CCRO pilot

3.1 Pilot Description

3.1.1 Technical data

Figure 28 shows schematically the various steps in the drinking water process at WPC De Blankaart. Based on the results of phase 1, the CCRO pilot was installed on a side stream after step 4 sand filtration. It is important to state that the pilot tests were executed before the planned renovation of the treatment works. The actual decantation and sand filtration will be respectively replaced by a flotation unit and dual media filters as presented in Figure 1. An improved water quality may be expected in the near future.

Figure 28: Actual drinking water treatment train in WPC De Blankaart. The CCRO pilot unit was installed in a side stream after the sand filtration.

The CCRO pilot was constructed by Waterleau with a capacity to produce 10-15 m³ permeate per hour. A video was made to describe the main components of the pilot ([description of pilot unit](#)). Water

from the feed raw water tank is transferred using the LP pump. On the discharge line of this pump there are four (4) consecutive injection points for sodium bisulfite (SBS), sulfuric acid, caustic soda and Memcare 1001 (antiscalant): SBS neutralize the residual chlorine in the feedwater. The caustic soda is only used during CIP cleaning (cleaning in place). Depending on the scaling potential of the feed water, antiscalant is dosed prior to the RO in order to reduce the scale formation in the RO membranes. Additionally Acid (H_2SO_4 50 % (w/w)) can be dosed to minimize the carbonate scaling.

The chemically pre-treated inlet water will then be further pressurized up to the required pressure to feed the reverse osmosis system. One of the two available piston pumps will act as the high-pressure pump. Upstream of the high pressure pump, the chemically conditioned RO feed water will flow through a set of cartridge filters. These have a 5-micron rating and act as a final guard to protect the reverse osmosis membranes for any possible particulate ingress. The chosen material of construction for the housings is stainless steel. The cartridge elements are made of polypropylene. The CCRO system consists of a single-stage pressure vessels array, skid mounted. In total there are three pressure vessels, each with five RO elements and one empty element (“deadman”). In total 15 FilmTec SOAR 4000i elements are installed with a total membrane area of 555 m² (37 m²/element). The skid is also fitted with a recycle pump that ensures that the circulation flow is sufficient to prevent polarization. The following pictures show the main components of the pre-treatment and CCRO system:

Figure 29: pictures of main components of CCRO pilot.

3.1.2 Operational settings

The pilot unit was operated from September 2022 to June 2023. The pilot plant could not be operated continuously during start-up due to frequent clogging of the cartridge filters. After replacement of

the cartridge filters, run times of less than 8 hours were reported. Visual observations revealed the presence of large particles (hundreds of micron to mm size) of activated carbon on the filter cartridges. Presence of activated carbon is not expected at this location of the treatment train. Apparently, backwash of carbon filters in the drinking water treatment line created a backflush of activated carbon particles towards the effluent canal of the sand filtration where the CCRO was connected. This problem was solved by the installation of an additional bag filter. Normal operation could only start from December 2022. Even after the installation of the additional bag filter, frequent clogging occurred. It was decided to replace the cartridges twice a week to maximize the operational time. The cause of clogging is discussed in 3.2.2.

During the test period, the operational settings were varied. In general, the test period is split in 5 distinct phases. The main settings are summarized in Table 9 and Table 10. Table 9 indicates the run period and setpoints for operation, water recovery, total run hours and run time ratio (calculated as the number of hours in operation divided by total time). Table 10 specifies the run times of the different phases. Table 9 indicates the run period and setpoints for operation, water recovery, total run hours and run time ratio. Table 10 specifies the run times of the different phases. The end of a cycle is based on this time setpoints. The results are further analyzed in detail in Section 3.3. Due to the clogging of the cartridge filters and other technical issues, the pilot could not run continuously.

Table 9: Main operational settings for CCRO during test period

Phase	Start date	End date	Flux setpoint (flux measured) l/m ² h	pH setpoint	Water recovery %	Total run time (h)	% of time in operation
0	27/09/2022	1/12/2022	-	-	-	-	-
1	1/12/2022	14/1/2023	18 (15)	no pH correction ¹	85%	210	19%
2	15/1/2023	31/3/2023	18 (17.7)	no pH correction	90%	599	33%
3	1/4/2023	17/4/2023	18 (16.3)	no pH correction	90%	230	56%
4	18/4/2023	16/5/2023	18	6.6	95%	308	44%

¹ The setpoint was 6.8 based on the software for scaling. Due to technical issues with the acid dosing, no pH correction was active. The pH of the incoming water was 6.8 to 7.

Phase	Start date	End date	Flux setpoint (flux measured) l/m ² h	pH setpoint	Water recovery %	Total run time (h)	% of time in operation
5	17/5/2023	6/6/2023	25 (16.8) (23.5)	6.6	95%	124	26%

Table 10: Average duration of feed and closed circuit phase

Phase	Feed phase (min:sec)	Closed circuit (min:sec)	Total time cycle (min:sec)
1	2:47	15:57	18:44
2	2:42	27:49	27:31
3	2:42	27:49	27:31s
4	2:41	49:46	52:27
5	2:25	37:53	40:17

3.2 Operational results

3.2.1 Feedwater quality

Chemical analyses were conducted weekly on a feed sample. The results are presented in Figure 30 to Figure 34. The composition of the feed water was relatively stable over the complete test period. Start-up did take place at the end of summer resulting in higher chlorides concentrations in the reservoir. Due to fresh water intake in October the chloride concentrations decreased. Runoff of nitrates combined with low microbiological activity (low temperatures) result in higher nitrate concentrations in winter time. The TOC concentration is stable over time (Figure 33). The concentration of silicates (Figure 34) decreases in spring. This is due to the rapid growth of diatom species as the temperature increases. A summary of the average composition is presented in Table 11.

Figure 30 : Concentration of anions in the feed water to the CCRO

Figure 31: Concentration of cations in the feed water to the CCRO

Figure 32: Concentration of total metals in the feed water to the CCRO

Figure 33: Concentration of TOC in the feed water to the CCRO

Figure 34: Concentration of silicates in the feed water to the CCRO

Table 11: Average composition of feed water

category	element	Mean	minimum	maximum
anion	NO ₂ - mg/L	0.0	0	0.02
	NO ₃ - mg/L	24.0	0	33
	Br - µg/L ²	0.0	0	0
	Cl - mg/L	165.4	141.03	234.1
	ClO ₂ - µg/L	0.0	0	0
	ClO ₃ - µg/L	93.7	66	147
	F - mg/L	0.2	0.21	0.24
	SO ₄ - mg/L	192.4	177.82	228.74
	PO ₄ - mg/l PO ₄	0.0	0	0
cation	Ba - µg/L	23.2	20	27
	Ca - mg/L	98.7	73.6	110.6

category	element	Mean	minimum	maximum
	K - mg/L	30.1	23.1	54.4
	Na - mg/L	110.0	93.7	158.7
metal	Al - µg/L	0.0	0	0
	As - µg/L	0.0	0	0
	B - µg/L	18.8	0	130.3
	Cd - µg/L	0.0	0	0
	Co - µg/L	0.3	0	0.4
	Cr - µg/L	0.0	0	0
	Cu - µg/L	0.5	0	10
	Fe - µg/L	31.2	0	142
	Hg - µg/L	0.0	0	0
	La - µg/L	0.0	0	0
	Mg - mg/L	16.1	14.6	18.4
	Mn - µg/L	4.3	0	17
	Mo - µg/L	0.0	0	0
	Ni - µg/L	5.0	5	5
	Pb - µg/L	0.0	0	0
	Sb - µg/L	0.0	0	0
	Se - µg/L	0.0	0	0
	Sr - µg/L	382.4	342	408
	Zn - µg/L	0.0	0	0
	V - µg/L	0.0	0	0
U - µg/L	0.0	0	0	
organic	TOC - mg/L	3.9	3.4	5.2
silicate	SiO ₂ - mg/L	6.2	2.7	9.6

3.2.2 Silt Density Index

The Silt Density Index (SDI) was measured regularly in the feed water (Figure 35). The SDI provides an indication of the fouling risk. The supplier of the membrane specifies a maximum SDI value of 5. During the test period, the SDI varied between 3.5 and 5.7 with a mean value of 4.9. Twice a SDI measurement was done in the feed water after the cartridge filter. The SDI values dropped to below 2. This indicates that the particles/elements that are responsible for the high fouling risk are largely removed by the cartridge filter. The cartridge filters had to be replaced twice a week because the maximum pressure drop was reached. One cartridge filter was sent to the company American Water Chemicals (AWC) for an autopsy (by Electron Microscopy and X-Ray Spectroscopy Analysis). This autopsy revealed that mainly iron and manganese were responsible for the clogging.

A high replacement frequency of cartridge filters is economically not acceptable for a full-scale unit. It can be concluded that the actual sand filtration units are ineffective as pre-treatment of the CCRO. De Watergroep is planning a renovation of the actual system and to upgrade the sand filters from a monolayer filter to a dual layer filter. After the renovation the scaling risk on the feed water needs to be re-evaluated. Even so, dual layer filtration might improve the situation, but it is clear that prefiltration will be an important factor for full-scale implementation and other options (e.g. UF) might be considered as well.

Figure 35: SDI-values in the feed water to the CCRO

3.2.3 Permeate quality

Chemical analyses were conducted weekly on a composite permeate sample. Over the runtime of one cycle, four samples were taken and combined into one composite sample. The results are presented in Figure 36 and Figure 37. All analyses for metals and silicates were below reporting limit.

Figure 36: Concentration of anions in the permeate water from the CCRO.

Figure 37: Concentration of cations in the permeate water from the CCRO.

3.2.4 Concentrate quality

Chemical analyses were conducted weekly on a composite concentrate sample. The concentrate was collected in a multibox (1 m³) and a grab sample was taken from the composite concentrate (about the concentrate of two cycles). The results are presented in Figure 38 to Figure 41.

Figure 38 : Concentration of anions in the concentrate from the CCRO

Figure 39: Concentration of cations in the concentrate from the CCRO.

3.2.5 Average concentrations and retention per phase

The average concentrations and the element retention is given in Table 12 to Table 15 for, respectively, anions, cations, metals and silicates. TOC-concentrates were not analyzed in the concentrate.

The average chloride retention is about 96-97% for the phases with a water recovery of 85 and 90%. After an increase of the water recovery to 95%, the retention decreases to 90%. For drinking water production a complete removal of ions is not required and even unwanted. A similar tendency is observed for nitrates where the retention decreases from 92% to 51%. Sulphates are completely retained by the membranes.

A similar tendency is observed for the cations. The retention for the monovalent ions Na and K is reduced at increasing water recovery. The bivalent cations Ca, Mg and Sr, metals and silicates are completely retained.

Table 12: Overview of chemical analyses (anions) for each phase with average element retention

Cl - mg/L				
	FEED	PERMEATE	CONCENTRATE	RETENTION
Phase 1	169	5	1124	97%
Phase 2	157	6	1370	96%
Phase 3	166	7	1386	96%
Phase 4	155	16	2119	89%
Phase 5	149	15	2108	90%
SO4 - mg/L				
	FEED	PERMEATE	CONCENTRATE	RETENTION
Phase 1	179	3	1230	98%
Phase 2	203	0	1943	100%
Phase 3	201	0	1914	100%
Phase 4	190	0	3715	100%
Phase 5	186	0	3850	100%
NO3 - mg/L				
	FEED	PERMEATE	CONCENTRATE	RETENTION
Phase 1	31	3	0	92%

Phase 2	32	8	209	75%
Phase 3	29	7	185	78%
Phase 4	24	12	192	51%
Phase 5	18	9	166	53%

Table 13: Overview of chemical analyses (cations) for each phase with average element retention

Ba - µg/L				
	FEED	PERMEATE	CONCENTRATE	RETENTION
Phase 1	22	0		100%
Phase 2	22	0	222	100%
Phase 3	25	0	221	100%
Phase 4	22	0	343	100%
Phase 5	24	0	364	100%
Ca - mg/L				
	FEED	PERMEATE	CONCENTRATE	RETENTION
Phase 1	93	0		100%
Phase 2	104	0	987	100%
Phase 3	107	0	961	100%
Phase 4	102	0	1574	100%
Phase 5	99	0	1534	100%
K - mg/L				
	FEED	PERMEATE	CONCENTRATE	RETENTION
Phase 1	34	1		98%
Phase 2	28	2	240	93%
Phase 3	26	2	231	93%
Phase 4	25	4	342	84%

Phase 5	25	4	331	86%
Mg - mg/L				
	FEED	PERMEATE	CONCENTRATE	RETENTION
Phase 1	15	0		100%
Phase 2	16	0	143	100%
Phase 3	16	0	148	100%
Phase 4	16	0	245	100%
Phase 5	16	0	238	100%
Na - mg/L				
	FEED	PERMEATE	CONCENTRATE	RETENTION
Phase 1	113	3		98%
Phase 2	108	7	933	93%
Phase 3	106	7	895	93%
Phase 4	100	15	1325	85%
Phase 5	98	13	1325	87%

Table 14: Overview of chemical analyses (metals) for each phase with average element retention

Fe - µg/L				
	FEED	PERMEATE	CONCENTRATE	RETENTION
Phase 2	8	0	104	100%
Phase 3	35	0	0	100%
Phase 4	33	0	219	100%
Phase 5	59	0	366	100%
Mn - µg/L				
	FEED	PERMEATE	CONCENTRATE	RETENTION
Phase 4	4	0	59	100%

Sr - µg/L				
	FEED	PERMEATE	CONCENTRATE	RETENTION
Phase 5	13	0	168	100%
Phase 1	378	0		100%
Phase 2	378	0	3692	100%
Phase 3	398	0	3605	100%
Phase 4	384	0	5834	100%
Phase 5	382	0	5651	100%

Table 15: Overview of chemical analyses (silicates) for each phase with average element retention

SiO ₂ - mg/L				
	FEED	PERMEATE	CONCENTRATE	RETENTION
Phase 1	10	0		100%
Phase 2	7	0	49	100%
Phase 3	3	0	24	100%
Phase 4	4	0	53	100%
Phase 5	5	0	71	100%

3.2.6 Chemical dosing

The specific chemical dose for acid, antiscalant and SBS is summarized in Table 16. Due to technical issues with the acid dosing and pH registration, a higher dosage of antiscalant was applied during phase 2 and 3. As pH setpoint was reduced to 6.6 in phase 4, the acid consumption also increased.

Table 16: Average dosage of chemicals per phase

	ppm H ₂ SO ₄	Antiscalant	ppm SBS
phase 1	-	2.9	5.7
phase 2	-	5.5	4.8
phase 3	-	4.3	4.0
phase 4	56.7	3.3	5.9
phase 5	47.0	2.8	3.3

3.2.7 Micropollutants

The presence of micropollutants was measured in some samples of feed and permeate. Additionally, micropollutants were analyzed in the concentrate twice. The list of micropollutants included in the monitoring program are listed in Table 17. The results are summarized in Table 18. Only 10 herbicides, 4 pharmaceutical compounds and 11 PFAS-components were detected in the feed above the detection limit. Most of these components are fully retained by the CCRO membranes. For the components with a low molecular weight, the retention was not absolute. For chlortoluron (MW 212.7 g/mol), metolachlor (MW 283.8 g/mol), 2,6-dichlorobenzamide (BAM - MW 190 g/mol) and metformin (165.6 g/mol) one permeate sample (out of three) was above the detection limit. As the detected concentrations are close to the reporting limit the % retention for individual components would result in high inaccuracies depending on the measured concentrations in feed and/or permeate are slightly above or below reporting limit. All permeate concentrations are below Flemish drinking water standards. In general it can be concluded that these retention for micropollutants is above 90%. The CCRO is an effective barrier for micropollutants. In order to guarantee the drinking water standards, modern treatment plants are based on a multibarrier concept. The water production plant in the Blankaart includes advanced oxidation (ozone/peroxide) and active carbon adsorption. Both treatment steps target the removal of micropollutants. By combining multiple steps, the drinking water standards can be guaranteed. All PFAS components are completely retained by the CCRO process. In the concentrate stream more micropollutants are detected due to the concentration. Note that some of the micropollutants detected in the feed stream are not detected in the concentrate stream. This can be explain by only twice a concentrate sample was analyzed simultaneously with the feed samples.

Table 17 : List of micropollutants included in the monitoring program.

pharmaceutical residues	PFAS		Pesticides	
ATENOLOL	10:2 FTS	PFECHS	Alachlor	METOBROM
BEZAFIBRAAT	4:2 FTS	PFHpA	AMETRYN	METOLACHL
CARBAMAZEPINE	6:2 diPAP	PFHpS	ATRAZIN	METOXURON
CLINDAMYCINE	6:2 FTS	PFHxA	BAM	METRIBUZIN
CLOZAPINE	6:2-8:2 diPAP	PFHxDA	BROMACIL	MONOLINUR
DIATRIZOAT	8:2 diPAP	PFHxS	CARBENDAZIM	PROMETRYN
DICLOFENAC	8:2 FTS	PFHxSA	CARBETAMIDE	Propachlor
DIMETRIDAZOLE	ADONA	PFNA	CHLORIDAZ	PROPAZIN
FENAZON	EtFOSA	PFNS	CHLOROXYUR	SEBUTYLAZ
FLUOXETINE	EtPFOSAA	PFOA	CHLORTOLU	SIMAZIN
GABAPENTINE	FBSA	PFODA	CYANAZIN	TERBUTRYN
IBUPROFEN	FOSA	PFOS	DESETHATR	TERBUTYLAZ
IOMEPROL	HFPO-DA	PFPeA	DESISOATRA	TERBUTYLAZINE_DESETH
IOPAMIDOL	MeFBSA	PFPeS	DESMETRYN	245T
IOPROMIDE	MeFOSA	PFTeDA	DIMETHENAMID	24D
IRBESARTAN	MeFOSA-Ac	PFTTrDA	DIURON	24DB
KETOPROFEN	MePFBSAA	PFTTrDS	FENURON	Bentazon
LIDOCAINE	PFBA	PFUnDA	HEXAZINON	DICHLORPROP
LINCOMYCINE	PFBS	PFUnDS	ISOPROT	MCPA
METFORMINE	PFDA	som EFSA-4	LENACIL	MCPB
METOPROLOL	PFDoDA	som PFAS	LINURON	MCPP
NAPROXEN	PFDoDS	som PFAS_TOT	METABENZ	CHLORMEQUAT
PARACETAMOL	PFDS		METALDEHYDE	CLOPYRALID
PENTOXIFYLLINE			METAMITRON	TRICLOPYR
PROPANOLOL			METAZACHL	
SOTALOL				
SULFAMETHOXAZOLE				
TRAMADOL				
TRIMETHOPRIM				

Table 18: Summary of micropollutants detected in feed and permeate stream (µg/l).

Type	component	#	Permeate		Feed		Flemish Quality standard
			Mean	Max	Mean	Max	
Herbicides	2,4-Dichlorophenoxy-acetic acid (2,4-D)	3	<0.020	<0.020	0.024	0.037	0.1
	2,6-dichlorobenzamide (BAM)	3	0.037	0.111	0.257	0.293	0.4
	Bentazon	3	<0.020	<0.020	0.108	0.111	0.1
	Chlortolu	3	0.007	0.02	0.052	0.073	0.1
	Clopyralid	3	<0.050	<0.050	0.069	0.079	0.1
	2-Methyl-4-ChloorPhenoxyAcetic acid (MCPA)	3	<0.020	<0.020	0.08	0.104	0.1
	Methaldehyde	3	<0.050	<0.050	0.022	0.066	0.1
	MetolaChl	3	0.009	0.026	0.05	0.072	0.1
	Terbutylazine_deseth	3	<0.020	<0.020	0.009	0.027	0.1
	Pharmaceutical compounds	Carbamazepine	3	<0.050	<0.050	0.021	0.062
Ibuprofen		2	<0.050	<0.050	0.042	0.083	
Metformine		2	0.033	0.033	0.717	0.924	
PFAS	Tramadol	3	<0.050	<0.050	0.018	0.054	
	FOSA	7	<0.001	<0.001	0	0.001	
	6:2 FTS	7	<0.001	<0.001	0.001	0.004	
	PFBA	7	<0.001	<0.001	0.007	0.009	
	PFBS	7	<0.001	<0.001	0.005	0.009	
	PFHpA	7	<0.001	<0.001	0.002	0.003	
	PFHxA	7	<0.001	<0.001	0.008	0.01	
	PFHxS	7	<0.001	<0.001	0.001	0.002	
	PFOA	7	<0.001	<0.001	0.003	0.003	
	PFOS	7	<0.001	<0.001	0.003	0.005	
	PFPeA	7	<0.001	<0.001	0.005	0.007	
	PFPeS	7	<0.001	<0.001	0	0.001	
	sum EFSA-4 ⁽¹⁾	7	-	-	0.007	0.010	0.004 ⁽²⁾
	sum PFAS	7	-	-	0.033	0.042	0.1

Type	component	#	Permeate	Feed	Flemish Quality standard
	sum PFAS_TOT	7	-	0.035	0.1

(1) EFSA-4 : sum of PFOS, PFOA, PFNA and PFHxS

(2) EFSA-4 is definite in the Flemish regulation as a quality objective

Table 19: Summary of micropollutants detected only in the concentrate (µg/l).

type	component	RO CONCENTRATE	
		Mean	Max
Herbicides	Atrazin	0.0245	0.028
	Chloridaz	0.0955	0.107
	Chlormequat	0.0885	0.109
	Desethatr	0.011	0.022
	Desisoatra	0.04	0.049
	Dichlorprop	0.056	0.056
	Dimethenamid	0.1775	0.206
	Diuron	0.059	0.068
	Isoprot	0.014	0.028
	Linuron	0.011	0.022
	Metabenz	0.0715	0.073
	Metamitron	0.028	0.056
	Metazachlo	0.163	0.2
	Methylchlorophenoxy-propionic acid (MCP)	0.255	0.255
	Metobrom	0.2005	0.213
	Simazin	0.0295	0.032
Pharmaceutical compounds	Terbutylaz	0.1835	0.218
	Trichlopyr	0.088	0.086
	Irbesartan	0.2325	0.295
	Metoprolol	0.033	0.066
PFAS	Sotalol	0.08	0.08
	8:2 FTS	0.0005	0.001
	FBSA	0.005	0.005
	PFDA	0.003	0.003
	PFNA	0.006	0.008

3.2.8 Specific energy consumption (SEC)

The specific energy consumption could not be derived directly from the experimental data. The pilot is designed to operate at higher flows and pressures. The pumps were operated at WPC The Blankaart outside their normal operational range. Specifically, the high pressure pumps required a minimal operating pressure to allow lubrication. The conductivity of the feed was relatively low and the required operating pressure was lower than setpoint. To overcome this issue, the pressure in the CCRO was shifted up with 3 bars by pinching the permeate valve at the outlet of the installation. As a result, a higher power consumption was noticed due to the increased operation pressure. Also, the frequent fouling of the cartridge filter caused an increase in power consumption. The specific energy consumption as measured during the pilot is given in Table 20 for information only.

Table 20: Specific energy consumption without correction for suboptimal operating conditions of the CCRO

Water recovery	SEC	
85%	0.892	kWh/m ³
90%	0.850	kWh/m ³
95%	0.889	kWh/m ³

The operational data of the CCRO pilot were provided to the University of Ghent to develop and calibrate a model for the CCRO process. The results are described in detail in the master dissertation “The utility of data generation to gain insight into the closed circuit reverse osmosis process” (Lozie, 2023). This model enables providing a good estimate of the SEC of a full-scale process. An average pump efficiency of 70% was taken into account. The results are summarized in Table 21. The numbers are in line with the energy consumptions for reversed osmosis systems. The claim that the CCRO process can be operated with lower energy consumption could not be confirmed by the pilot test.

Table 21: Specific energy consumption with correction for suboptimal operating conditions of the CCRO (Adapted from Lozie H, 2023)

Water recovery	SEC	
85%	0.494	kWh/m ³
90%	0.548	kWh/m ³
95%	0.615	kWh/m ³

3.3 Technical conclusions

Within B-WaterSmart, it is investigated if a lower dependence on the raw water quality can be achieved by means of a Closed Circuit Reverse Osmosis (CCRO) installation. CCRO results in extensive removal of chlorides and acts as a barrier to micropollutants, increasing the performance of the installation and thus relaxing the tolerance levels for intake of raw water to the reservoir. CCRO differs from conventional RO systems by a cyclic operational mode. Main benefits are a higher flexibility towards varying incoming water quality, low sensitivity for scaling and high water recovery. Especially a high water recovery is a key success factor for De Watergroep given the water scarcity and limited storage capacity. For conventional RO systems with a typical water recovery around 70-80%, potential benefits of relaxation the intake limits would be eliminated by the higher water losses in the production.

In the period September 2022 until June 2023 a CCRO pilot (10 m³/h) was run at the water production plant of the Blankaart, Diksmuide. After initial challenges, the location (after the sand filtration) appeared to work well when a two-step prefiltration was installed. The water recovery of the CCRO was gradually increased from 85% to 95%. Even at this high water recovery the CCRO process remained stable and no indications of scaling were observed. The chloride retention was about 90% and micropollutants (pesticides, pharmaceuticals, PFAS) were retained to concentrations below drinking water standards.

CCRO is a promising and a potentially highly efficient membrane technology. Especially the high water recovery is essential for successful integration. The study was not conclusive on the specific energy consumption (SEC). Although CCRO claims to be more energy efficient compared to standard reverse osmosis, this claim could not be validated due to technical limitations of the pilot.

4 Pilot study Aquafin: Effluent reuse from WWTP Woumen

4.1 WWTP description

The WWTP of Woumen is a medium-sized WWTP of 18,000 inhabitant equivalents (IE_{BOD54}), with a year-round average flow rate of $12,491 \text{ m}^3/\text{d}$ (2023) and a minimal dry weather flow of around $2,500 \text{ m}^3/\text{d}$. The installation is designed for a maximum capacity of $27,734 \text{ m}^3/\text{d}$, which is six times the theoretical daily dry weather flow for a 14-hour time window (6Q14). Figure 42 and Figure 43 show the timeseries and the distribution of the flow rate of WWTP Woumen in the period 2019 – 2023.

Figure 42: Time series of the influent flowrate of WWTP Woumen during the last five years.

Figure 43: Histogram of the influent flowrates of WWTP Woumen during the last five years.

Figure 44 shows the geographical location of WWTP Woumen and WPC De Blankaart. Figure 45 shows the aerial layout of the WWTP.

Figure 44: Geographical situation of the Woumen case. A: WWTP Woumen; B: effluent discharge into the Houtensluisvaart; C: the IJzer river; D: WPC De Blankaart.

Figure 45: Aerial layout of WWTP Woumen. A: location of the pilot installation; B: effluent discharge into the Houtensluisvaart.

The treatment train consists of a grit filter (6 mm), a sand trap, an oxidation ditch for biological treatment, and clarifiers. The effluent is discharged into the Houtensluisvaart, a small canal that discharges into the IJzer river. The geographical distance between the WWTP of Aquafin and WPC De Blankaart is 1.7 km. In 2023, the effluent contained on average 2.1 mg/L BOD (97% removal), 29 mg/L COD (88% removal), 11 mg/L SS (93% removal), 5.1 mg/L total nitrogen (82% removal) and 0.5 mg/L total phosphorus (87% removal).

4.2 Water intake quality requirements of De Watergroep

4.2.1 Identification of problematic parameters

As explained in Section 1.4, the problematic parameters that should be reduced in any case are identified based on the 'minimal effluent polishing' scenario in which polished WWTP effluent will be added to the buffer basin and thus undergoes the complete drinking water treatment. The quality

requirements used as a reference are based on the intake requirements De Watergroep applies for the intake of raw surface water. After the planned upgrades of the WPC are executed (see section 1.3), these intake requirements might change and become less stringent.

Not for all parameters, intake requirements exist. Therefore, the intake requirements are supplemented with (i) concentrations generally found in the raw surface water and/or in the buffer basin, (ii) with legal drinking water quality criteria from the European Drinking Water Directive (EU 2020/2184) and the Flemish drinking water decree from VMM (Vlaamse overheid, 2023) and (iii) target values for surface water quality for sustainable drinking water production from the European River Memorandum (ERM, 2020). Note that polished WWTP effluent need not to meet drinking water quality criteria, as long as sufficient treatment can be ensured by the drinking water treatment.

Table 22 shows the comparison between the water quality of unpolished WWTP effluent and the various requirements. Effluent quality values are based on:

- Nutrients and chloride--> several measurements from WWTP Woumen of 2019
- Heavy metals --> several measurements from WWTP Woumen of 2019
- Salts and conductivity --> three analyses from WWTP Woumen of 2021
- Other trace elements --> single analysis from WWTP Woumen of 2021
- Organic micropollutants --> several measurements from several WWTPs (excluding very small ones) in the period 2010 – 2022 from a structured campaign of VMM
- Pathogens --> several measurements from several WWTPs from various internal research projects (non-structural campaign)

Table 22: Comparison between the water quality of unpolished WWTP effluent and the various requirements.

Parameter	Unit	Mean conc effluent	Max conc effluent	1 st Intake requirements from De Watergroep	2 nd Intake requirements from De Watergroep	Mean conc raw surface water	Max conc raw surface water	Mean conc buffer basin	Max conc buffer basin	EU-directive 2020/2184	Flemish decree	Surface water guidelines ERM
Inorganics												
NO ₃ ⁻	mg/L	21.4	48.7	40	60					50	50	25
PO ₄ ³⁻	mg/L	1.6	4.6	1	2							
NH ₄ ⁺		0.4	2							0.5 ⁽¹⁾	0.5 ⁽¹⁾	0.3
NO ₂ ⁻	mg/L	0.082	0.3							0.5	0.5	
Cl ⁻	mg/L	152	260	150	250					250 ⁽¹⁾	250 ⁽¹⁾	100
EC	µS/cm	1,175	1,503	1,000	2,000					2,500 ⁽¹⁾	2,500 ⁽¹⁾	700
Metals and trace elements												
Al	µg/L									200 ⁽¹⁾	200 ⁽¹⁾	
As	µg/L	2	3							10	10	
B	mg/L	<0.21	<0.21							1.5	1.5	
Br	mg/L	0.15	0.21									
Ca	mg/L	72	88									
Cd	µg/L	<0.2	<0.2							5	5	
Cr	µg/L	<3	<3							25 (from 2036)	50	
Cu	mg/L	0.004	0.006							2	2	
F	mg/L	0.18	0.18							1.5	1.5	1
Fe	µg/L									200 ⁽¹⁾	200 ⁽¹⁾	
Hg	µg/L	<0.02	<0.02							1	1	
K	mg/L	32	41									
Mg	mg/L	12	15									
Mn	µg/L									50 ⁽¹⁾	50 ⁽¹⁾	
Na	mg/L	128	173							200 ⁽¹⁾	200 ⁽¹⁾	
Ni	µg/L	8	10							20	20	
Pb	µg/L	1	1							5 (from 2036)	10	
Sb	µg/L									10	10	
Se	µg/L									20	10	
SO ₄ ²⁻	mg/L	103	128							250 ⁽¹⁾	250 ⁽¹⁾	100

Parameter	Unit	Mean conc effluent	Max conc effluent	1 st Intake requirements from De Watergroep	2 nd Intake requirements from De Watergroep	Mean conc raw surface water	Max conc raw surface water	Mean conc buffer basin	Max conc buffer basin	EU-directive 2020/2184	Flemish decree	Surface water guidelines ERM
U	µg/L									30	30	
Zn	µg/L	47	59								5,000 (target 200)	
Pesticides												
Chlormequat	µg/L			0.1	0.2							
Metaldehyde	µg/L			0.1	0.2							
Clopyralid	µg/L			0.2	0.7							
Bentazon	µg/L	0.12	>40	0.3	0.8							
Other pesticides	µg/L	0.25 ⁽⁴⁾	>100 ⁽⁴⁾	1	5					0.1	0.1	0.1 - 1 ⁽⁵⁾
Sum of pesticides	µg/L			5	10					0.5	0.5	
Other micropollutants												
Pharmaceutical compounds	µg/L	0.4 ⁽²⁾	30 ⁽²⁾					0.1 ⁽³⁾	1 ⁽³⁾			0.1 - 1 ⁽⁵⁾
Microbiological indicators												
<i>E. coli</i>	cfu/100mL	10 ³ -10 ⁶				<5•10 ³	2.5•10 ⁴	<2•10 ³	1.2•10 ⁴	0	0	10 ³
Total coliform bacteria	cfu/100mL	10 ⁴ -10 ⁷				<5•10 ⁴	2.5•10 ⁵	<5•10 ³	1.3•10 ⁵	0 ⁽¹⁾	0 ⁽¹⁾	
Enterococci	cfu/100mL	10 ² -10 ⁴								0	0	4•10 ²
<i>C. perfringens</i>	cfu/100mL	10 ² -10 ⁵								0 ⁽¹⁾	0 ⁽¹⁾	

(1) Indicator value, no strict requirement.

(2) Analysis includes 26 pharmaceutical compounds.

(3) Analysis includes 10 medicines, not all of those are included in 2.

(4) Analysis includes 69 pesticides.

(5) Depending on whether the substance was already evaluated and whether biological effects were identified.

Based on this overview table, some problematic parameters can be identified.

- Despite WWTP's focus on **nutrients (phosphate, nitrate and ammonium)**, these parameters are still not sufficiently low in the effluent to achieve the intake criteria. For phosphate, there is no drinking water limit and the criteria from De Watergroep are intended to avoid biological growth and algae bloom in the reservoir.
- Salt content in the WWTP effluent is too high. **Chlorides and conductivity** should be reduced
- **Pesticides** don't meet drinking water standards in the WWTP effluent. Occasionally, the concentrations are higher than the intake criteria meaning that no sufficient removal can be guaranteed by the current drinking water treatment.
- No specific requirements for **pharmaceutical compounds** are in place yet. However, their concentrations in the WWTP effluent are definitely higher compared to the current concentrations in the buffer basin so their removal requires some attention.
- **Microbiological indicators** have higher concentrations in the effluent compared to the current raw intake water. Considering the source of municipal waste water, the presence of other human pathogens cannot be excluded. The polishing of effluent water needs to provide enough disinfection to guarantee microbial safety of the drinking water.
- Bromide levels do not exceed any standards. However, due to the presence of ozone in the drinking water treatment, bromate formation must be kept under control.
- The organic content of the WWTP effluent could not be compared directly with the drinking water standards since other parameters are used for assessing the organic content (BOD and COD in waste water vs TOC and DOC in drinking water). However, it can be assumed that the organic content of the effluent should be lowered to reduce the potential for biological growth. Moreover, the presence of organics and suspended solids will hamper the operational efficiency of several treatment technologies.

4.2.2 Technology choice

The removal rates of key problematic parameters, as identified in section 4.2.1, via conventional treatment technologies are summarized in Table 23. This technology matrix also makes an assessment whether the presence of suspended solids might be an issue.

Table 23: Expected removal rates of key parameters of conventional post-treatment technologies.

Treatment Technology	Suspended Solids	Suspended Solids in Inflow Is a Problem?	Phosphate	Nitrate	Chloride/EC	Pesticides	Pharmaceuticals	Pathogens
Drum Filter	30-80% (f)	No	No Significant Removal					
Sand Filter	50-99% (b)	Sometimes	No Significant Removal	40-90% (d)	No Significant Removal	0-50% (d)	0-50% (d)	1-3 log (g)
UF	>99% (b)	Often	No Significant Removal	2-6 log (f)				
NF	N/A	Yes	30% (a)	10-30% (c)	10-50% (c)	85-98% (c)	85-98% (c)	3-6 log (c)
RO	N/A	Yes	99% (b)	84-96% (c)	90-99% (c)	90-98% (c)	90-98% (c)	>4-7 log (c)
UV	No Removal	Sometimes	No Significant Removal	No Significant Removal	No Significant Removal	Only at high doses	Only at high doses	1-4 log (f)
Activated Carbon	N/A	Yes	No Significant Removal	No Significant Removal	No Significant Removal	30-80% (e)	30-80% (e)	1-2 log (g)
Ozone	N/A	Yes	No Significant Removal	No Significant Removal	No Significant Removal	30-80% (e)	30-80% (e)	2-6 log (g)
Ion Exchange	N/A	Yes	95% (h)	90% (h)	> 90% (c)	No Significant Removal	No Significant Removal	No Significant Removal
Electrodialysis	N/A	Yes	70-90% (i)	Up to 85% (g)	85->95% (i)	No Significant Removal	No Significant Removal	No Significant Removal

(a) own results Aquafin; (b) VITO, 2020; (c) Metcalf & Eddy, 2007; (d) STOWA, 2006; (e) STOWA, 2015; (f) Deutsche Vereinigung für Wasserwirtschaft, Abwasser und Abfall, 2019; (g) World Health Organization 2017; (h) Terry, 2009; (i) Zhang, 2013.

From this technology matrix, it is evident that - to remove all targeted components - a combination of technologies is required. The excessive amount of chloride is the most challenging problem to solve. Reverse osmosis (RO), Ion exchange or Electrodialysis will be necessary to achieve the quality requirements for chloride. Ion exchange and electrodialysis have no effect on organic micropollutants, such as pesticides and pharmaceuticals, or pathogens, the need for additional micropollutant removal, for example by ozone and or activated carbon, and an additional disinfection, for example by UV or by chlorine, arises. Since RO is very efficient in removing most of the key problematic parameters, this is chosen as the most relevant technique for pilot tests. It is likely that the water quality will be sufficient for the “minimal effluent polishing” scenario after treatment with RO.

As direct application of RO to the WWTP effluent is unfeasible due to the heightened risks of biofouling and blockage, a pre-treatment step employing an ultrafiltration membrane (UF) is required. This UF membrane on its turn will be preceded by a screen to prevent frequent clogging by

high suspended solids (SS) in the effluent (mean SS = 12.7 mg/L and maximum SS = 30 mg/L as of 2019).

RO treatment exhibits exceptional efficacy in eliminating salts, nutrients, pathogens and many micropollutants. Consequently, the resulting water quality is expected to surpass the requirements for the “minimal effluent polishing” scenario, and it might be advantageous to consider alternative scenarios such as injecting the polished effluent into a later stage of the drinking water treatment. Skipping the pretreatment of the WPC however, would decrease the amount of barriers for nutrients, suspended solids and organic material. These parameters might require close monitoring. Furthermore, additional expected limiting parameters for the intake point include some micropollutants permeating through RO and the number of safety barriers related to pathogen mitigation, mainly because the mixing with the large buffer volume is skipped losing the ability to dilute calamities. To achieve further removal of micropollutants, a granular activated carbon (GAC) adsorption unit is added after the RO treatment. The pilot test will show whether this is required. Furthermore, an ultraviolet (UV) disinfection module is included to augment microbiological removal. Evaluation of the microbiological removal barriers will be conducted using the QMRA+ tool (B-WaterSmart #26).

Should the use of WWTP effluent as a source be combined with (partial) RO in the drinking water treatment, then the use of RO could be reassessed, since there will be no need for chloride or conductivity removal. Different techniques might be employed for removing micropollutants and pathogens separately. However, even if the need for salt removal is eliminated, the use of RO remains interesting as a very effective barrier against organic micropollutants and pathogens.

With a new Urban Waste water Treatment Directive (UWWTD) being implemented, some WWTPs might be upgraded with a quaternary treatment step targeting micropollutants. For the moment, the UWWTD is imposing quaternary treatment steps to achieve 80% removal of some indicator substances. It is unlikely this will be sufficient to meet guidelines listed in Table 22 for all parameters. However, when the goals are set a bit stricter, it might be unnecessary to consider organic micropollutants as problematic parameters. In this case, mainly nutrients, salts and pathogens remain, and it might be beneficial to look at ion exchange or electro dialysis in combination with one or several disinfection techniques instead of using RO, but this should be confirmed by QMRA.

4.3 Description of the pilot installation and the pilot tests

4.3.1 Pilot installation

A pilot installation was commissioned (BOSAQ, Belgium) for the treatment of the effluent of WWTP Woumen. The pilot was constructed in a 20 ft High Cube container (Figure 46).

Figure 46: Pilot container at WWTP Woumen.

The pilot consisted of several treatment technologies, organized in modules:

- Prefiltration and ultrafiltration (UF)
- Reverse osmosis (RO)
- Granular activated carbon (GAC) and ultraviolet disinfection (UV)
- Chemical dosage

The full treatment train therefore consisted of UF-RO-GAC-UV. This is depicted in Figure 47. The treatment train can be modified to test different combinations of technologies, by bypassing individual modules. This can be done by manually adjusting valves and selecting the desired treatment train in the control software.

Figure 47: Full treatment train (UF – RO – GAC – UV) of the pilot installation, including chemical dosage.

The installation is controlled through the cloud logging platform, coupled to the pilot's PLC. Using remote access, the user can operate the pilot and visualize its parameters. Figure 48 shows the main dashboard of the control platform, which can be accessed through the online platform.

Figure 48: Main dashboard of the control platform of the pilot.

From the main dashboard, the individual modules can be visualized (Figure 49, Figure 50, Figure 51, Figure 52). This allows the user to monitor the sensor values and component statuses. By selecting an individual component (e.g., a pump, valve or sensor), a pop-up appears to allow manual control of the component.

Figure 49: Prefiltration and UF module.

Figure 50: RO module.

Figure 51: GAC + UV module.

Figure 52: Chemical dosage module.

The different modules are briefly described below.

4.3.1.1 Prefiltration and UF module

The effluent of the WWTP is first collected in a 500 L buffer tank. Next, it is prefiltered by a prefilter, type Minitwist, with a stainless steel mesh (mesh sizes 100 or 200 μm).

The ultrafiltration unit consists of a single-stage DuPont IntegraPac™ IPD51-XP with hollow-fiber polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) membranes with an active surface area of 51 m^2 and a pore size of 0.03 μm . The influent is fed outside-in and dead-end. The UF module is designed for a theoretical recovery of 95% and flux of 40 – 140 $\text{L}/\text{m}^2/\text{h}$. The UF filtrate is stored in a 500 L filtrate buffer tank.

During operation, both the prefilter and UF membrane are periodically cleaned, the prefilter through a vortex procedure, the UF through a backwash procedure. This is initiated when the programmed TMP (trans membrane pressure) is exceeded, or the maximum filtration time is reached. The maximum pressure drop, above which the pilot will initiate ‘abort’ mode and the operation will halt, is 4 bar for the prefilter, and 2.1 bar for the UF membrane. Therefore, the programmed pressure drops to initiate self-cleaning and backwash should be lower than these maximal values. The backwash of the UF consists of an air scour, followed by a gravitational drain, a backwash through the top outlet, a backwash through the bottom outlet, and a forward flush.

Additionally, the UF membrane needs periodic chemical cleaning through a cleaning in place (CIP) procedure. This is manually initiated after 1 – 6 months of operation and may consist of a regular backwash followed by and acid (pH 2) or alkaline (pH 12) CIP in recirculation or soak mode, and air scour, and finally one or several regular backwash steps until the pH is neutralized again.

Table 24 lists the initial settings of the UF module during normal operation (values provided by Bosaq).

Table 24: Initial settings of the UF module, normal operation.

Parameter	Standard configuration
Flush flowrate (m ³ /h)	1.8
Flux	Flux at 25°C: 40 - 140 L/m ² /h
Filtration flowrate (m ³ /h)	1.8
Backwash flowrate UF (m ³ /h)	5
Backwash flowrate prefilter (m ³ /h)	4.5
Duration filtration cycle	1 h
Duration flush	2 min 30 sec
Duration backwash UF top	30 sec
Duration backwash UF bottom	30 sec
Duration gravitational drain	30 sec

The UF module is equipped with the following sensors:

- Flow transmitter feed flow
- Flow transmitter UF backwash flow
- Level transmitter feed water tank
- Level transmitter permeate water tank
- Pressure transmitter before prefilter (feed side)
- Pressure transmitter between prefilter and ultrafilter
- Pressure transmitter after ultrafilter (permeate side)
- Conductivity transmitter permeate
- Temperature transmitter permeate
- Turbidity transmitter before intake in the pilot container (in the WWTP effluent channel)
- Turbidity transmitter between prefilter and ultrafilter
- Turbidity transmitter after ultrafilter (permeate side)

4.3.1.2 RO unit

The treatment train of the RO module starts with a 5 µm prefilter consisting of five polypropylene cartridges with a maximum pressure of 10 bar, as a safety measure to remove any solids if the UF module loses integrity or if any solids enter into the system (e.g. biofilm growth).

The two RO membranes are installed in a two-stage configuration and consist of spiral-wound polyamide thin-film composite membranes (FilmTec™ BW30XFRLE-400/34) with an active surface area of 37 m² each. The module is designed for a flux of 13.5 L/m²/h at a permeate flow of 1 m³/h.

A high-pressure pump is used for the feed flow, with a maximum pressure of 25 bar. This pump is fed from the UF permeate tank. Part of the concentrate of the second RO stage is recirculated to the feed pump. This way, the concentrate can be recycled over the RO module to increase the overall recovery. The RO permeate is stored in a 500 L buffer tank and continues towards the GAC-UV module when the maximum level is reached.

Before each operation, the RO module starts with a flush procedure using RO permeate, to initiate the membranes and avoid damage by high pressures, flow rates or hydraulic shocks. This flush is performed at low pressure and flow rate. If there is no RO permeate available for the flush step, UF permeate can be used.

When the actual filtration phase starts, the feed pressure is gradually increased until the desired concentrate flow rate is reached. After that, the flow is automatically regulated by continuously adjusting the valve positions. The initial RO permeate is wasted until the conductivity has decreased below the desired value of 50 µS/cm, after which it is redirected to the permeate buffer.

Table 25 lists the initial settings of the RO module during normal operation (values provided by Bosaq).

Table 25: Initial settings of the RO module, normal operation.

Parameter	Standard configuration
Recovery (%)	50
Flux	13.5 L/m ² /h at 15°C and 1 m ³ /h RO permeate
Feed flow (m ³ /h)	1.5
Recirculation flow (m ³ /h)	4.1
Forward flush flow (m ³ /h)	1.5
Permeate conductivity threshold (µS/cm)	50
Duration permeate to waste	5 min
Duration RO flush	4 min 50 sec

The RO module is equipped with the following sensors:

- Flow transmitter feed flow (feed side, before mixing point with recirculation flow)
- Flow transmitter recirculation flow (before mixing point with feed flow)
- Flow transmitter permeate flow
- Flow transmitter concentrate flow
- Level transmitter permeate water tank
- Pressure transmitter suction side of the feed pump (feed side)
- Pressure transmitter feed pressure (before prefilter)
- Pressure transmitter between prefilter and RO

- Pressure transmitter concentrate RO stage 1 / feed RO stage 2
- Pressure transmitter RO permeate
- Pressure transmitter after RO permeate distribution pump
- Pressure transmitter TO recirculation
- Conductivity transmitter feed (feed side, before mixing point with recirculation flow)
- Conductivity transmitter feed and recirculation (feed side, after mixing point with recirculation flow)
- Conductivity transmitter permeate
- pH transmitter feed and recirculation (feed side, after mixing point with recirculation flow)
- Temperature transmitter permeate

A CIP procedure of the RO membranes may be needed when the pressure drop of the RO membranes has increased by 10 – 15%, the normalized permeate flow has dropped by 10%, or the normalized salt passage has increased by 5 – 10%. Depending on the nature of the fouling (i.e., scaling or organic/biological fouling), different CIP procedures are required. The CIP solution can be either acidic (HCl at pH 2) or alkaline (NaOH at pH 12) and be supplemented by direct in-line dosage of antiscalant and biocide.

4.3.1.3 GAC-UV module

The GAC-UV module is fed by RO permeate, and its feed flowrate equals the flowrate of the RO permeate.

The GAC filter consists of a 712 L vessel filled with a bottom layer of 100 kg sand (grain size 3 – 5 mm), topped with a bed of 250 kg AquaSorb™ 1200 granular activated carbon with a specific surface area of 950 m²/g and a particle size of 12x40 mesh. The designed minimal feed flow is 1 m³/h and the empty bed contact time (EBCT) is 43 min at filtration flow of 1 m³/h.

The UV unit is equipped with a 40 W 254 nm UV-lamp with an intensity of 0.36 W/m². The system is designed for a residence time of 32 sec at a flow rate of 1 m³/h. The effluent of the GAC-UV unit is stored in a 750 L buffer tank.

When the GAC filter reaches a pressure drop above 1.5 bar or the desired filtration time (initial setpoint is 168h) is reached, it is backwashed and rinsed to avoid channeling.

Table 26 lists the initial settings of the GAC+UV module during normal operation (values provided by Bosaq).

Table 26: Initial settings of the GAC+UV module, normal operation.

Parameter	Standard configuration
Backwash flowrate	5.6 m ³ /h
Rinse flowrate	1 m ³ /h

The AC-UV module is equipped with the following sensors:

- Flow transmitter feed flow AC
- Flow transmitter AC backwash flow
- Flow transmitter AC filtrate flow / UV feed flow
- Level transmitter permeate water tank
- Pressure transmitter AC feed
- Pressure transmitter AC filtrate
- Pressure transmitter AC backwash
- Temperature transmitter on the UV lamp
- Turbidity transmitter AC feed
- Turbidity transmitter AC permeate
- UV irradiance transmitter

4.3.1.4 Chemical dosage module

The chemical dosage unit consists of five stock solutions connected with chemical dosage pumps:

- NaOCl against biofouling and protein fouling. Should only be used for the UF module
- NaOH for alkaline CIPs
- HCl for acidic CIPs
- Antiscalant for direct in-line feeding during RO operation
- Biocide for direct in-line feeding during RO operation

The CIP chemicals can be automatically added to a 208 L CIP vessel to produce the desired CIP solution at the desired pH for cleaning the UF or RO modules. The CIP solution is prepared using RO permeate. During a CIP procedure, the solution is continuously recirculated to the CIP vessel to monitor the temperature, pH and oxidation-reduction potential (ORP). When these values exceed the set threshold, the CIP solution is drained and refilled with clean permeate.

Table 27 lists the initial settings of the chemical dosage module during normal operation (values provided by Bosaq).

Table 27: Initial settings of the chemical dosage module, normal operation.

Parameter	Standard configuration
CIP flowrate	1.5 m ³ /h
CIP solution volume	100 L

The chemical dosage module is equipped with the following sensors:

- Flow transmitter CIP supply/recirculation
- Level transmitter CIP tank
- Pressure transmitter CIP supply/ recirculation

- Conductivity transmitter CIP solution
- Redox potential transmitter CIP solution
- pH transmitter CIP solution
- Temperature transmitter CIP supply/recirculation

4.3.2 Pilot tests

The pilot installation was operational between 16/02/2023 and 26/03/2024. Operational challenges prevented continuous operation of the pilot plant, particularly during periods of poor effluent quality conditions resulting from rainy weather. Section 4.5 describes the operational challenges, mainly occurring at poor effluent conditions. Despite a testing period of over 1 year, the actual operational hours are limited.

In November 2023, the region of Woumen was faced with flooding. Heavy rainfall causes the flooding of the river Yser, resulting in the closure of the surrounding areas near the water treatment plant due to flooded roads and pastures. During the flooding period, the turbidity of the WWTP effluent exhibited significantly high values. Consequently, the installation could not be operated during this period.

Table 28 provides a summary of the samples collected during the piloting phase. Given the absence of test data at poor effluent conditions, the samples are unable to represent worst case effluent quality for some parameters, as will be clear from Section 4.4.1. Nevertheless, valuable experience regarding expected outcome concentrations and removal efficiencies are obtained.

The abundance and removal of micropollutants was addressed in several ways. At first, Aquafin took some samples that were analyzed on a set of 19 common medicines. This was done 2 times (17/08/2023 and 28/09/2023) for all intermediate samples when treating the water with UF-RO-GAC-UV and one time (05/03/2024) when treating the water with UF-GAC. The samples of 17/08/2023 were also assessed for PFAS. Secondly, De Watergroep analyzed 10 packages comprising 246 compounds focusing on removal by RO and subsequently by GAC at 2 moments in time (17/08/2023 and 09/10/2023). The package covering 25 medicines was analyzed again at a third moment in time (22/02/2024), focusing on removal by RO and additionally checking removal by UF and recovery in the RO concentrate. Finally, on 25/10/2022, a semi-quantitative screening of the effluent of WWTP Woumen was performed by the French laboratory Lodiag, Targeting 867 pollutants.

Table 28: Overview of samples.

Date	Analysis of organics, nutrients and salts	Analysis of Iron & Alumina	PFAS analysis	Limited micropollutant analysis	Extended micropollutant analysis (at DWG)	Microbiology	Flow [m ³ /day]
16/03/2023	UF						14.223
23/03/2023	UF, RO, GAC, UV						15.154
29/03/2023	UF, RO, GAC, UV					UF	13.654
03/04/2023	RO, GAC, UV					UF	18.837
19/04/2023	UF, RO, GAC, UV					UF	9.334
27/04/2023	UF, RO, GAC, UV						14.067
03/05/2023						UF	8.422
22/05/2023	UF, RO, GAC, UV						6.679
05/07/2023	Drain UF	Drain UF					10.884
17/08/2023	UF, RO, GAC, UV	UF	UF, RO, GAC, UV	UF, RO, GAC, UV	RO, GAC	UF	4.772
28/09/2023	UF, RO, GAC, UV			UF, RO, GAC		UF	4.290
09/10/2023	UF, RO, GAC, UV				RO, GAC		3.811
21/02/2024	UF, RO, GAC, UV				UF, RO (only pharmaceuticals)		17.631
05/03/2024	GAC			GAC			23.566

4.4 Results

In this section, all measurements below LOQ are set equal to LOQ for plotting and calculation of the removal rates. The impact of measurements below LOQ on the calculated removal rates is discussed.

4.4.1 Water quality progress

This section assesses the compliance of the predefined problematic parameters to specific criteria outlined in Table 22. The intake criteria of De Watergroep are the most critical to meet. Additionally, the recommendations from the European River Memorandum are incorporated in the evaluation, to evaluate the adherence to recognized good practices. The graphs in this section show the distribution of concentrations after each treatment step in a boxplot. Additionally, the concentration distribution in the waste streams (backwash from the ultrafilter and concentrate from the RO-unit) are displayed. The red line indicates the second intake requirement of De Watergroep (above this, no intake possible), the orange line indicates the first intake requirement of De Watergroep (above this, only intake if the buffer content is under pressure) and the green line is the recommendation for raw surface water from the European River Memorandum.

Nutrient concentrations after each treatment step are represented in Figure 53 and Figure 54. Nutrient treatment by the WWTP is susceptible to weather conditions and worst-case nutrient concentrations occur at rainy weather, when the residence time in the WWTP is short. Due to operational problems, the pilot did not run in these conditions and inlet concentrations of nitrate and phosphorus are always meeting the inlet criteria of De Watergroep. From Table 22 above, it is clear that this is not always the case and at least a 20% removal of nitrate and an 80% removal of phosphate is required to achieve the intake requirements from De Watergroep. De Watergroep has no criteria for ammonia, but the observed values in the effluent are exceeding the recommendations from the European river memorandum. For nitrate and ammonia, no reduction in concentration is observed after ultrafiltration. After reversed osmosis, their concentrations are significantly reduced. Single high concentrations of ammonia were observed at a sampling moment in March 2024, when the RO was bypassed. The concentrations of orthophosphate are already very close to the detection limit at the inlet, posing challenges in drawing comprehensive conclusions regarding removal efficiency. From the concentration profiles, it can be estimated that some removal takes place at the ultrafiltration stage, although no elevated concentrations are observed in the backwash. Before reversed osmosis, orthophosphate concentrations were generally below or very close to LOQ, after reversed osmosis no orthophosphate were observed. Elevated concentration of orthophosphate in the RO concentrate indicates that there is indeed removal taking place in the reversed osmosis unit.

Figure 53: Nitrate and ammonium concentrations after each treatment step of the pilot plant. The red line indicates the second intake requirement of De Watergroep (above this, no intake possible), the orange line indicates the first intake requirement of De Watergroep (above this, only intake if the buffer content is under pressure) and the green line is the recommendation for raw surface water from the European River Memorandum. The amount of measurements is indicated above each boxplot with the amount of measurements above LOQ indicated between brackets.

Concentration of Orthophosphate

Figure 54: Orthophosphate concentrations after each treatment step of the pilot plant. The red line indicates the second intake requirement of De Watergroep (above this, no intake possible), the orange line indicates the first intake requirement of De Watergroep (above this, only intake if the buffer content is under pressure) and the green line is the recommendation for raw surface water from the European River Memorandum. The amount of measurements is indicated above each boxplot with the amount of measurements above LOQ indicated between brackets.

Chloride concentrations and conductivity are represented in Figure 55. Chloride concentrations in the effluent are susceptible to weather conditions and worst-case salt concentrations occur at dry weather, when there is no dilution. Due to operational problems, the pilot did not run in conditions with rainy weather, but since these conditions would introduce dilution, it is assumed that the pilot tests are representative for worst case effluent conditions concerning salt content. The inlet concentrations of the pilot almost always exceed the criteria from De Watergroep concerning chloride and conductivity. Ultrafiltration does not affect the conductivity or the chloride content significantly. Reversed osmosis on the other hand is very effective in reducing both chloride content and conductivity and is resulting in concentrations far below the criteria from de Watergroep and even the European River Memorandum.

Figure 55: Chloride and conductivity concentrations after each treatment step of the pilot plant. The red line indicates the second intake requirement of De Watergroep (above this, no intake possible),

the orange line indicates the first intake requirement of De Watergroep (above this, only intake if the buffer content is under pressure) and the green line is the recommendation for raw surface water from the European River Memorandum. The amount of measurements is indicated above each boxplot with the amount of measurements above LOQ indicated between brackets.

Several micropollutants were targeted in the analysis. Of all micropollutants, pharmaceutical compounds are of special interest since they are typical to the source of municipal effluent and therefore exceed concentrations normally found in raw surface water, as explained in Section 4.2.1.

The compounds targeted in the Lodiag screening include mainly parent compounds of drugs and pesticides, but also some metabolites and narcotics are included, see Figure 56.

Figure 56: Target compounds of chemical analysis subdivided by type.

Detected compounds are categorized in 5 clusters according to their presence, see Figure 57. These categories depend on the dilutions used. According to the European River Memorandum, anthropogenic substances in surface water for drinking water production should not be present in concentrations higher than 0.1 – 1 µg/L (depending on whether the substance was already evaluated and whether biological effects were identified). According to the intake criteria from De Watergroep, individual pesticides for example should not exceed 1 µg/L (1st intake requirement) or 5 µg/L (2nd intake requirement). The general limit for individual pesticides in drinking water is 0.1 µg/l. If there are indications that the individual pesticide is not removed by the existing drinking water treatment, more stringent restrictions will be imposed. For pharmaceutical residues, no general limit value is defined and an individual risk assessment is required. For a limited number of pharmaceutical residues precaution values are derived. In accordance with the preceding concentration plots, these limits are indicated by a green, an orange and a red line on the scheme showing the five clusters in Figure 57. It is important to stress that the results may not be representative. The application of pesticides depends on the growth season. The consumption of medicines may also show a seasonal pattern. Insufficient data are available to assess this seasonal variation.

Figure 57: Five clusters for categorizing micropollutant results from Hydroscreen, a screening service from Lodiag.

The results of the screening are displayed in Table 29 and Figure 58. 31 compounds were detected in the secondary and it is assumed they are all exceeding the limit of $0.1 \mu\text{g/L}$ set out by the European River Memorandum. 6 compounds (Chloridazon, Tramadol, O-Desmethyltramadol, Diclofenac, Valsartan, Amitriptyline), of which one pesticide (Chloridazon), potentially exceeded the intake criteria of De Watergroep for individual pesticides. Note that, except for Diclofenac, these are all other compounds than screened by Aquafin. Only for diclofenac, an individual drinking water precaution value for Flanders has been derived by VMM ($0.3 \mu\text{g/l}$) (2022, Vlaamse Milieumaatschappij).

Table 29: Results of the Hydroscreen micropollutant screening of the WWTP Woumen effluent.

Estimated concentration in $\mu\text{g/L}$	Drug	Drug Metabolite/ Drug	Drug Metabolite	Pesticide	Pesticide Metabolite	TOTAL
	Detected. Not quantified	3	0	0	0	
< 0.25	9	2	0	5	1	17
0.25 to 0.5	3	1	0	1	0	5
0.5 to 2.5	3	0	1	0	0	4
2.5 to 5.0	0	0	0	0	0	0
> 5.0	1	0	0	1	0	2
TOTAL	16	3	1	7	1	28

Figure 58: Results of the Hydroscreen micropollutant screening of the WWTP Woumen effluent.

From the 19 substances that were analyzed by Aquafin, all were found at least once in the effluent and the effluent after UF, except for furosemide. Several are present above 0.1 µg/L and some even above 1 µg/L. At the two sampling moments from Aquafin during operation of the UF-RO-GAC-UV treatment train, all targeted compounds were removed until below LOQ by RO, except for benzotriazole and sum of 4- and 5-methylbenzotriazole. The removal is confirmed by the elevated concentrations of several compounds in the RO concentrate. For benzotriazole and sum of 4- and 5-methylbenzotriazole, GAC could achieve an additional removal, but not enough to reduce the compound below LOQ and for benzotriazole even not enough to get below 0.1 µg/L, as illustrated in Figure 59.

Figure 59: Concentrations of the 19 selected substances after the UF, RO and GAC steps of the pilot. The red line indicates the second intake requirement of De Watergroep (above this, no intake possible), the orange line indicates the first intake requirement of De Watergroep (above this, only intake if the buffer content is under pressure) and the green line is the recommendation for raw surface water from the European River Memorandum. For boxplots indicated with a star, both results are below LOQ. Parameters indicated in orange are present above detection limit after GAC and parameters indicated in red above 0.1 µg/L.

On the other hand, at the sampling moment where RO was bypassed, the GAC filter in the pilot is not able to remove all compounds below LOQ and some of them remain present even above the recommended concentration of 0.1 µg/L of the European River Memorandum (see Figure 60).

Figure 60: Concentrations of the 19 selected substances before and after GAC (without preceding RO). The red line indicates the second intake requirement of De Watergroep (above this, no intake possible), the orange line indicates the first intake requirement of De Watergroep (above this, only intake if the buffer content is under pressure) and the green line is the recommendation for raw surface water from the European River Memorandum. For boxplots indicated with a star, the result is below LOQ. Parameters indicated in orange are present above detection limit after GAC and parameters indicated in red above 0.1 µg/L.

PFAS are not detected in any of the samples that Aquafin took on 17/08/2023, not even in the RO concentrate.

In the analysis from De Watergroep, 66 compounds (of 246 analyzed) were detected after UF. Amongst them are both pesticides and medicines. Concentrations of medicines (mean 0.56 µg/L) generally exceed concentrations of pesticides (mean 0.17 µg/L). Benzotriazole and derivatives also occur in decent amounts (mean 0.80 µg/L). Concentrations exceeding 0.1 µg/L occur regularly. From the 4 pesticides with specific intake criteria from De Watergroep, bentazon (maximum concentration 2.2 µg/L) and clopyralid (maximum concentration 0.45 µg/L) exceed the second and the first intake criteria respectively. Metaldehyde was found, but in low concentrations and chlormequat could not be detected. Concentrations exceeding 1 µg/L occur mostly with medicines, but were also found with benzotriazole and some pesticides. Table 30 shows the maximum concentration of pollutants after UF occurring at least once above 1 µg/L.

Table 30: Maximum detected concentrations of pesticides and medicines after the UF stage of the pilot.

Compound	Maximum concentration detected	Date of maximum concentration
Carbamazepine	1.413 µg/L	09/10/2023
Diclofenac	1.991 µg/L	09/10/2023
Gabapentine	1.662 µg/L	17/08/2023
Irbersartan	1.225 µg/L	09/10/2023
Sotalol	1.223 µg/L	09/10/2023
Tramadol	2.187 µg/L	09/10/2023
Dimethenamid	1.82 µg/L	17/08/2023
1H-Benzotriazole	1.496 µg/L	09/10/2023
Bentazon	2.192 µg/L	17/08/2023

Out of these 66 compounds, 7 are PFAS. They could be detected since the detection limits of DWG are lower than the once applied on the samples taken by AQF. None of the PFAS was detected in a concentration higher than 0.02 µg/L (the current LOQ in commercial analysis) and the total amount detected is an order of magnitude lower (<0.05 µg/L) than the drinking water limit (0.5 µg/L).

At all three sampling moments from De Watergroep, none of the 246 pollutants were detected above LOQ after RO, except for benzotriazole and 5-M-1H-Benzotriazole are passing RO, and also GAC is not able to remove the residuals of these compounds below LOQ. The precaution value for 1H-benzotriazole in drinking water is 4.5 µg/l and the detected values remain below this value. No precaution value exists for 5-M-1H-Benzotriazole.

From the drug analysis from the Watergroep at 22/02/2024 it is clear that no removal is observed during the ultrafiltration step, as was expected. RO concentrate measurements on this date show elevated concentrations, confirming removal by RO.

Pathogens were addressed by analyzing some indicator organisms using a Quanti-Tray (IDEXX) before and after UF. Figure 61 shows the counts for *E. coli* and coliforms before UF. After UF, no coliforms or *E. coli* could be detected.

Figure 61: Counts of coliforms and *E. coli* in secondary effluent.

As shown in Figure 62, suspended solids are present in significant concentrations in the WWTP effluent. After UF, no suspended solids are detected anymore. High concentrations of suspended solids in the backwash confirm the very good removal of suspended solids by UF. COD is removed slightly by UF and completely by RO. Elevated concentrations in UF backwash and RO concentrate confirm removal by both UF and RO. On the contrary, BOD (Figure 63) could not be detected in UF permeate and also not in RO concentrate, indicating it is largely removed by the UF. Analysis below detection limit hamper the reliable calculation of removal rates.

Concentration of Suspended solids

Concentration of Chemical oxygen demand

Figure 62: SS and COD concentrations after each treatment step of the pilot. The green line is the recommendation for raw surface water from the European River Memorandum. The amount of measurements is indicated above each boxplot with the amount of measurements above LOQ indicated between brackets.

Concentration of Biological oxygen demand

Figure 63: BOD concentrations after each treatment step of the pilot. The green line is the recommendation for raw surface water from the European River Memorandum. The amount of measurements is indicated above each boxplot with the amount of measurements above LOQ indicated between brackets.

Bromide was not analyzed during these pilot tests.

4.4.2 Removal efficiencies

Figure 64 illustrates the calculated removal rates of nutrients and salts. As expected, based on the concentration profiles, no significant removal is observed during ultrafiltration, but a significant

removal (70 – 80%) is observed during reversed osmosis. Calculated removal for orthophosphate is low for both the UF and the RO stage. As is clear from Section 4.4.1, measurements close to the detection limit prevent the calculation of reliable removal rates. Actual removal rates are expected to be in line with the highest results in Figure 64, as these are not biased by the LOQ. How many removal rate calculations are biased by LOQ's can be known from Figure 53, where the amount of samples above LOQ is indicated. As evident from the concentration profiles in Section 4.4.1, RO demonstrates high efficacy in removing chloride and conductivity, yielding removal rates exceeding 90%.

Figure 64: Removal of selected salts in the UF and RO stages of the pilot.

Removal of pharmaceuticals by RO and GAC (with and without preceding RO) is illustrated in Figure 65. Note that the calculation of the removal rate is strongly disturbed by measurements below LOQ. All boxes reaching to 0% emerge from measurements below LOQ. Actual removal rates are expected to be in line with the highest results in Figure 65, as these are not biased by the LOQ. For some compounds, no single reliable removal rate could be calculated since all measurements in the outflow

are below LOQ. These compounds can be known from Figure 59 (for RO) and from Figure 60 (for GAC), where it is indicated with a * if all measurements are below LOQ.

Note that the even the highest calculated removal by GAC is modest, with rates not significantly surpassing 60%. These highest calculated removals are not biased by measurements below LOQ. On the contrary, RO reaches removal efficiencies exceeding 90%, although all measurements after RO are below LOQ, so actual removal efficiencies will be >90%. Similar as with the concentration profiles, the removal benzotriazole shows distinct behavior. This is the only compound with measurements above LOQ after RO, so the calculation of the removal rate by RO is representative (not biased by LOQ) and it is not reaching 40%. For benzotriazole, GAC seems to be more efficient.

Figure 65: Removal percentages of 19 selected substances by the RO and GAC units.

Since no *E. coli* or coliforms could be detected after UF, the removal by UF is at least 3 log (since the LOD of the methodology used is 1 cfu/100 mL). This confirms the assumptions of Table 23 based on literature. Although no *E. coli* or coliforms are detected after UF, this does not mean there is sufficient pathogen removal by only using UF. For potable reuse, it is recommended to implement a multibarrier system and perform a QMRA analysis. The QMRA tool (B-WaterSmart DAP5) is applied to this case in the design phase of the pilot. In this analysis, a direct potable reuse (without residence time in the buffer basin) was assumed. In this case rapid sand filtration was predicted to be insufficient as a pretreatment to reduce the infection risk for protozoa to an acceptable level. However, when using nanofiltration, both the infection risk and DALY (Disability-adjusted life years) are predicted to be at acceptable levels. It is therefore assumed that the proposed treatment train containing an RO treatment step, will be sufficient to deliver an acceptable QMRA result. The results of the QMRA are also described in deliverable 3.5 “The water cycle modelling and assessment

solutions toolkit – Final results”. An extract of this report is added in annex 1. This will have to be confirmed when there are plans to scale up the pilot.

Analysis below detection limit hamper the reliable calculation of removal rates. Nevertheless, the calculated removal rates confirm previous conclusions based on concentration profiles, that suspended solids and BOD are removed until below LOQ by the UF, so no removal can be calculated for RO. On the contrary, the removal of COD is taking place in both the UF and the RO module (Figure 66). After RO, COD could not be detected above LOQ (see Figure 62), so actual removal rates by RO will be higher.

Figure 66: Removal of SS, COD and BOD in the UF and RO stages of the pilot.

4.5 Operational challenges

4.5.1 Variations in effluent quality

Secondary treated effluent from a Waste water Treatment Plant (WWTP) still contains some organic matter and nutrients, making it a biologically active matrix and therefore challenging to treat. Moreover, the quality of secondary effluent in Woumen exhibits regular fluctuations, depending on the incoming flowrate of sewage to the WWTP, which is significantly influenced by prevailing meteorological conditions.

At the inlet of the WWTP in Woumen, sewage is elevated using one or two screw pumps. An increase in influent flow triggers the activation of the additional screw pump to facilitate the passage of water through the purification process. The simultaneous engagement of two screw pumps augments the throughput of the installation, causing inadequate settling time within the final settling tanks. Consequently, the turbidity of the secondary effluent increases, and even some sludge might be washed out. This may alter the characteristics of the organic matter in the secondary effluent, making it more biologically active.

This phenomenon is exemplified through data from 7/03/2023, as delineated in Figure 67 and Figure 68. With escalating levels of the influent buffer at the WWTP, an additional screw pump is activated. The abrupt initiation of the second screw pump results in an elevated flow rate of the WWTP effluent and a subsequent sudden increase in effluent turbidity. Throughout the duration of the second pump's operation, turbidity persists at an elevated yet relatively stable level.

Figure 67: Effect of influent level at the WWTP on activation of screw pumps (7/03/2023)

Figure 68: Relationship between flow rate and turbidity of the WWTP effluent (7/03/2023)

When the secondary effluent exhibits a high turbidity (> 15 mg/L suspended solids), a polyelectrolyte is dosed during the treatment process of WWTP in Woumen. This polyelectrolyte binds to the sludge, enhancing sedimentation and preventing sludge from being washed out with the effluent. At the start of the testing period, the polyelectrolyte use at the WWTP in Woumen is a cationic polymer from Clarflok, from the type AQE 84. The dosing point is at the outlet of the aeration tank, just before entering the settlers.

4.5.2 Prefiltration clogging

The prefilter of the pilot installation is from the type Minitwist (Pelmar Engineering). It has a self-cleaning functionality based on vortex formation within the filter. The period between two cleanings is denoted as a filtration cycle. During a filtration cycle, the pressure drop over the filter rises as a result of filter clogging. The initial pressure drop in a filtration cycle is an indication of the efficiency of the preceding cleaning. The trigger to start self-cleaning varies over the testing period.

Next to the automatic self-cleaning, there is also a possibility to manually clean the prefilter to remove additional dirt that cannot be removed during the self-cleaning procedure.

4.5.2.1 Examples when prefiltration clogging occurred

Figure 69 represents the turbidity (suspended solids content) and the pressure drop across the prefilter on 23/03/2023 when the pilot ran with a flow rate of 1.8 m³/h and a prefiltration screen of 100 µm. Self-cleaning takes place when the filtration cycle of the ultrafilter comes to an end (see

Section 4.5.2.2). These timeseries illustrate that the pressure drop across the prefilter depends on the quality of the feedwater (i.e. secondary treated effluent. When turbidity rises, the pressure drop across the prefilter increases more rapidly (steeper slope). From these data, a relationship between turbidity in the effluent and clogging speed off the prefilter can be inferred, as illustrated in Figure 70. Here, the average turbidity in the UF feed water (before prefiltration) is displayed in relation to the increase in pressure drop across the prefiltration unit. An R^2 value of 0.60 was found, indicating a fair level of linear correlation between both parameters. This implies that higher turbidity in the secondary effluent typically results in a faster increase in pressure drop across the prefilter, and thus a faster clogging.

Figure 69: Impact of feed water turbidity (suspended solids) on pressure drop across the prefilter (23/03/2023).

Figure 70: Relationship between pressure change (i.e. speed of clogging) across the prefilter and average turbidity (suspended solids) in UF feed water.

On 03/04/2023, the pilot ran with a flow rate of 1.8 m³/h and a prefiltration screen of 100 μm. Self-cleaning takes place when the filtration cycle of the ultrafilter comes to an end (see Section 4.5.2.2). The pressure drop and the flow rate are shown in Figure 71. The initial pressure drop across the prefilter registers at 0.4 bar during the first filtration cycle. The pressure drop over the prefilter rises significantly during each cycle, indicating the occurrence of fouling. Consistent pressure at the start of the first three cycles indicates effective removal of accumulated contamination during filtration. However, by the fourth cycle the initial pressure drop has increased compared to the previous cycles, indicating that accumulated contamination could not be removed efficiently and thus that the self-cleaning is not effective. During this fourth filtration cycle, the pressure drop exceeds 3 bar, and consequently, the feed pump is no longer capable of delivering a flow rate of 1.8 m³/h, impeding the replenishment of the filtrate buffer vessel at an adequate pace.

Figure 71: Impact of elevated pressure drop over the prefilter on flow rate and transmembrane pressure over the ultrafiltration.

When the self-cleaning procedure is insufficient to restore the original initial pressure drop, the prefilter screen must be cleaned manually. The screening is done through an inside-out principle. However, contamination is primarily visible on the exterior, as can be seen in Figure 72. This is likely due to biofilm formation resulting from intake of water with high biological activity and frequent plant downtime. The contamination that is actually leading to increased initial pressure drops, is mainly located in the filter pores and is thus not immediately visible. Manual cleaning is effective in removing contamination, restoring the initial pressure to 0.2 bar, as shown in Table 31.

Figure 72: Visual effect of manual prefilter cleaning.

Table 31: Effect of manual cleaning of the prefilter on the initial pressure in the next filtration cycle.

Date	Initial pressure		
	Before manual cleaning [bar]	After manual cleaning [bar]	Reduction [%]
22/03/2023	3.47	0.234	93
19/04/2023	0.315	0.256	19
21/02/2024	0.342	0.246	28

To mitigate the rapid increase in pressure drop across the prefilter during periods of high feedwater turbidity, on 27/04/2023, the 100 µm screen was replaced with a 200 µm screen. This adjustment resulted in an acceptable pressure drop across the prefilter, as depicted in Figure 73, which now consistently remains below 3 bar. Consequently, the filtration flow rate of 1.8 m³/h can be maintained, as anticipated. However, the pressure drop (trans membrane pressure - TMP) across the ultrafiltration membrane started to rise rapidly due to the passage of larger particles through the prefilter. The initial pressure of 0.4 bar cannot be reached in each filtration cycle, after each self-cleaning. Since, it is clear that the 200µm screen is not protective enough, it was switched back to the 100 µm screen. The effect on the ultrafiltration membrane caused by this fouling event, will be discussed in Section 4.5.3.1.

Figure 73: The impact of switching the prefilter screen from 100 µm to 200 µm on the pressure drop across the prefilter and the UF membrane (27/04/2023).

Figure 74 represent the level of the ultrafilter filtrate tank (as an indication of flow through the pilot) and the pressure drop across the prefilter on 06/02/2024, when the pilot ran with a flow rate of 1.8 m³/h and a prefiltration screen of 100 µm. Self-cleaning takes place when the pressure drop over the prefilter exceeds a preset trigger, first of 0.35 bar and later of 0.3 bar (see Section 4.5.2.2). 06/02/2024 is a day with good effluent conditions, which implies that the incoming flow rate to the WWTP is low, with only one screw pump in operation, resulting in no significant turbidity peaks. The average turbidity of the WWTP effluent is 3.79 mg/L suspended solids. On average, every 15 minutes, corresponding to once per filtration cycle, a self-cleaning of the prefilter occurs. This is temporarily halting filtration, so no new filtrate is produced during this self-cleaning, which can be observed through the slight decrease in the ultrafiltration filtrate tank level. This self-cleaning frequency is semi-acceptable because sufficient filtrate is being produced to facilitate the eventual backwash of the UF module and to enable the RO to function normally with a reduced feed flow rate of 1 m³/h.

Figure 74: Maximizing performance on a dry day (6/02/2024).

Figure 76 represent the level of the ultrafilter filtrate tank (as an indication of flow through the pilot) and the pressure drop across the prefilter on 19/02/2024, when the pilot ran with a flow rate of 1.8 m³/h and a prefiltration screen of 100 µm. Self-cleaning takes place when the pressure drop over the prefilter exceeds a preset trigger of 0.5 bar (see Section 4.5.2.2). 06/02/2024 is a day with bad effluent conditions. The utilization of a second screw pump to handle the incoming flow rate at the WWTP leads to a peak in turbidity of the WWTP effluent, as depicted in Figure 75. Consequently, the pressure drop across the prefilter increases very fast, almost continuously triggering the self-cleaning of the prefilter (every few minutes). This results in insufficient generation of new UF filtrate to refill

the filtrate tank completely after backwashing. As a consequence, the filtrate buffer ends at a lower level after each backwash. Self-cleaning is only allowed when there is a certain level in the filtrate tank. In the third cycle, this level requirement is not consistently met, allowing the pressure drop over the prefilter to increase, despite the trigger for self-cleaning at 0.5 bar. It is clear that with these high needs for self-cleaning, it is not possible to run the ultrafiltration module in a stable way while keeping the pressure drop over the prefilter under control. Moreover, it can be noticed that, in contrary to what is seen in the time series of 06/02/2024 (Figure 74), the initial pressure drop of each filtration cycle is not always below 0.3 bar. This might imply that the pressure drop across the prefilter should not exceed 0.35 bar to avoid accumulation of persistent fouling and manual cleaning of the prefilter. Furthermore, the use of the prefilter on days when the WWTP effluent has high turbidity may pose challenges because self-cleaning is needed too frequently and the prefilter seems to be very prone to accumulation of persistent fouling.

Figure 75: Turbidity (suspended solids) of WWTP effluent due to activation of screw pumps (19/02/2024).

Figure 76: Maximizing performance on a wet day (19/02/2024).

4.5.2.2 Potential causes for clogging

From the experimental experiences described above, a few potential causes for clogging of the prefilter can be identified.

A first potential cause for clogging is the presence of suspended solids in the effluent, mainly at rainy weather conditions and elevated flow rates, resulting in high turbidity of the secondary effluent. Especially fluctuating flow conditions resulting in a fluctuating effluent quality are apparently difficult to handle for the prefilter, more than constant bad quality conditions. Polyelectrolyte dosing at the WWTP at turbidities above 15 mg/L suspended solids might further induce persistent fouling, however this could not be proven from the experiments.

The visible biofilm at the filtrate-side of the prefilter indicates that the water has a high potential for biological activity. This is not a surprise, given the concentrations of nutrients and BOD in the secondary effluent (see Section 4.2.1). Increased nutrient and organics content and even a potential sludge wash out in rainy weather conditions will only increase the potential for biological activity and biofilm formation. The pilot is out of operation most of the time. With no flow through the filter and in the pipes, biofilm can thrive even more.

The supplier mandates that the pressure drop across the prefiltration must not exceed 0.3 bar to prevent accumulating persistent fouling and prevent the need for regular manual cleaning. However, prior to 25/08/2023, no trigger could be set to activate self-cleaning based on a specific pressure

drop across the prefiltration or reaching a certain TMP. Self-cleaning only occurs when a backwash of the UF membrane is activated, which occurs when the UF filtrate vessel is filled (90%) or at the end of the filtration cycle of the ultrafilter (preset time period, see Section 4.3.1.1). This results in frequent exceeding of the proposed maximum pressure of 0.3 bar, as is clear from the examples in Section 4.5.2.1. Accumulation of persistent fouling can occur when the pressure drop rises and the filter cake is compacted and pressed deeper into the filter screen. This prevents the pressure from returning to its initial level after filtering heavily contaminated water, as self-cleaning is not sufficient to remove the accumulated persistent contamination.

Prior to 06/03/2024, the self-cleaning procedure did not work properly due to an incorrect fitting. Due to this unsuitable fitting, the prefilter is failing to clean all parts to the same extent. Only the top part of the screen is cleaned thoroughly. The remaining test period after 06/03/2024 is too short to identify the effect of correcting the fitting in the clogging behavior of the filter. Effluent quality is rather bad in the last weeks of the pilot tests and clogging still appears.

4.5.2.3 Prefiltration cleaning optimization

Several actions were taken during pilot test to optimize the cleaning of the prefiltration and prevent clogging.

At first, regular manual cleaning interventions were carried out, more or less every 2 weeks. A second action, which was very important, is the decoupling of UF backwash and prefilter self-cleaning on 25/08/2023. Substantially, the pressure drop trigger value to initiate self-cleaning was systematically lowered to about 0.3 bar to prevent persistent clogging, yielding stable behavior in dry weather conditions. Furthermore, water with turbidity exceeding 20 mg/L suspended solids is never treated in the pilot installation to prevent overload of the prefiltration. When the turbidity exceeds 15 mg/L suspended solids for more than 30 minutes, the installation is also shut down, to prevent substantial amounts of PE residues from entering the pilot installation. At last, the prefilter was equipped with the correct orifice valve for optimal self-cleaning on 06/03/2024.

4.5.2.4 Additional recommendations to enhance prefiltration.

Several actions can be taken to enhance the performance of prefiltration at bad effluent conditions when scaling up this application.

A prefiltration in multiple steps with varying cut-of values can decrease the load of suspended solids on one prefiltration step. When upscaling this technology train, several types of prefiltration become available. One could opt for a system with a more continuous self-cleaning, and preferably a backwash mechanism instead of a vortex suction cleaning system. Moreover, it will be advantageous if advanced cleaning (e.g. with chemicals or at elevated pressure) is possible in an automated way. An example of such a system is a disk filter.

In addition, it is good to take another look at the control and design of the WWTP itself. WWTPs are currently optimized only to meet the standards for discharge into the watercourse, not to prevent

fluctuations, for example. In the case of reuse, it may be useful to see if the coupling of the WWTP and post-treatment can be improved through minor modifications enhancing for example the stability of effluent quality or the dosing of electrolyte. If major modifications are needed, further consultation is needed regarding responsibilities.

Due to the high potential for biological growth of the water, it might be a good idea to design the prefiltration step a bit bigger than what the technical requirements prescribe, giving some margin for efficiency loss. Moreover, it is recommended to introduce redundancy with two filters in parallel, so there is no interruption in operation if one of the filters needs cleaning. Additionally, it can be recommended from these tests, to not trust the stated recovery, as with secondary effluent you might need a higher frequency of cleaning requiring water and thus end with a lower water efficiency. Another recommendation is to do a slight pre-disinfection before prefiltration, for example with low doses of chlorine. This will quench the high potential for biological growth and delay the formation of biofilm to elongate the filtration cycles. If chlorine is used, neutralization of the excess of chlorine is afterwards required to protect the RO membranes.

The pressure drop of the prefilter should not exceed the limits recommended by the supplier. To achieve this, it is important that each filtration step can be operated independently. Preferably, there is enough buffer capacity between each filtration step and automatic flow reduction, in order to cope with fluctuating cleaning frequencies.

Lastly it is important to check whether all components are correctly dimensioned and installed in order for the filter to work optimally.

4.5.3 Membrane fouling in the ultrafiltration unit

4.5.3.1 Examples when UF membrane fouling occurred

Soon after installation, it becomes evident that the backwash of the UF is unable to restore the initial pressure of 0.15 bar. As can be seen in the pressure drop (trans membrane pressure - TMP) profile from 23/03/2023 (see Figure 77), the initial pressure rises slightly in every filtration cycle. In March 2023, the weather conditions were rainy, and the pilot plant experienced highly fluctuating feed quality conditions. Despite efforts to avoid operation in the event of polyelectrolyte dosing, occasionally, elevated loads of suspended solids (> 10 mg/L) reached the pilot plant. This resulted in fluctuating turbidity levels after the pre-filter, occasionally exceeding values of > 10 NTU. In combination with the complex nature of organic material, these levels proved to be too heavy a load for the ultrafiltration membrane.

Figure 77: Increase of the TMP in the UF module (23/03/2023).

On 27/04/2023 the initial TMP had increased to about 0.4 bar. A mini-CIP was performed using NaOCl, this is similar to a normal CIP (cleaning in place), but with shorter circulation times. However, after the mini-CIP, the initial pressure stayed at 0.4 bar.

As mentioned in Section 4.5.2.1, additionally on 27/04/2023, the 100 μm screen was replaced with a 200 μm screen to cope with the frequent clogging of the prefilter. This adjustment caused the TMP across the ultrafiltration membrane to rise even more rapidly due to the passage of larger particles through the prefilter. The initial TMP of 0.4 bar cannot be reached in each filtration cycle, after each self-cleaning. The initial pressure is increasing fast, even surpassing 1 bar in about 8 hours, as can be seen in Figure 73. Since, it is clear that the 200 μm screen is not protective enough, it was switched back to the 100 μm screen on 09/05/2023.

After some manual flushing, the initial pressure could again be diminished to 0.35 bar. However, accumulation of fouling continued. On 22/05/2023 and 23/05/2023, the pilot ran continuously for almost 24 hours and it is clear that the accumulation fouling is increasing with every cycle, see Figure 78.

Figure 78: Impact on the pressure drop over the prefilter and the TMP over the UF after switching back from 200 μm screen to 100 μm screen in the prefilter (22/05/2023 - 23/05/2023).

After 23/05/2023 (during the period June 2023 to December 2023), the TMP of the UF never returned to the original initial level of 0.2 bar. At the beginning of each operational cycle it starts around 0.75 bar, steadily rising. Several actions were taken to try to clean the membrane, such as more frequent backwashing, more air scour during the backwash, triggering the backwash based on TMP, elongating the CIP procedure and including a CIP with acid. All adaptations to the backwash and CIP procedure will be discussed in more detail in Section 4.5.3.3. None of the actions was sufficient to restore the original initial TMP of 0.2 bar. Because of the frequent cleaning needs of the UF (and the prefilter), the recovery of the UF unit dropped and it was no longer capable of providing the RO unit with 1.5 m^3/h . Therefore, the flow through the RO unit was decreased on 01/06/2023 to 1 m^3/h .

On 25/01/2024, the UF membrane was replaced with a new membrane. The effect is immediately noticeable. The initial pressure now stabilizes around 0.15 bar. Based on previous results, it is decided to continue working with a prefilter screen of 100 μm , not allowing the pressure across the prefilter to exceed 0.35 bar and avoiding prolonged operation at rainy weather conditions and elevated effluent turbidity. The filtration time of the UF membrane is set to 30 minutes and the backwash trigger is set to 0.2 bar to ensure that no contamination adheres to the membrane and to prevent clogging issues. Throughout the remaining operational period the TMP did never reach the backwash

trigger of 0.2 bar. The TMP profile of the new membrane at low effluent turbidity and high (medium) effluent turbidity respectively can be seen in Figure 74 and Figure 76.

4.5.3.2 Potential causes for UF fouling

From the experimental experiences described above, a few potential causes for fouling of the ultrafilter can be identified, many of them similar to the potential causes for clogging of the prefilter, as described in Section 4.5.2.2.

Similar to the prefilter, a first potential cause for clogging is the presence of suspended solids in the effluent, mainly at rainy weather conditions and elevated flow rates, resulting in high turbidity of the secondary effluent. Polyelectrolyte dosing at the WWTP at turbidities above 15 mg/L suspended solids might further induce persistent fouling, however this could not be proven from the experiments. According to the membrane supplier, especially cationic polymer has the ability to irreversibly block membrane pores.

Given the concentrations of nutrients and BOD in the secondary effluent (see Section 4.2.1), the effluent has a high potential for biofouling. Increased nutrient and organics content and even a potential sludge wash out in rainy weather conditions will only increase the potential for biological activity and biofilm formation. The pilot is out of operation most of the time. With no flow through the filter and in the pipes, biofouling can thrive even more.

Since TMP rises steadily during operation, an efficient backwash is important to restore the initial pressure drop in every filtration cycle and prevent too high TMP's. As can be seen from the examples in Section 4.5.3.1, this is not the case in the pilot in Woumen. Section 4.5.3.3 will elaborate further on how backwash could be optimized.

Accumulation of persistent fouling can occur when the TMP rises and the pollution is pressed deeper into the membrane pores. This prevents the pressure from returning to its initial level after filtering heavily contaminated water, as backwash is not sufficient to remove the accumulated persistent contamination. Apparently, the TMP's that were allowed in the beginning of the test period were much higher than what is recommended for the membrane and no option to trigger backwash based on TMP was available before 25/08/2023.

It is recommended to do a mini-CIP 1 – 3 times a week at continuous operation. Due to practical reasons, this was not possible in the pilot installation. Since the operational hours were quite low, it was estimated that a lower frequency of mini-CIP would be sufficient. Because of low CIP frequency, fouling might have had the time to become more persistent. Section 4.5.3.3 will elaborate further on how CIP could be optimized.

An autopsy was carried out on the first membrane after its replacement to check the type of fouling that is most present.

Using SEM (scanning electron microscopy) images, the morphological structure of membrane fouling was examined. EDS (energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy) analyses were conducted to determine the presence of chemical elements in the fouling layer and on the membrane surface.

The results, show that the fibers are covered with a black, fibrous deposit (see Figure 79). On the inlet side of the UF membrane, a fouling layer with amorphous structures at the bottom and a covered, amorphous growth structure with loose particles on the top is observed. The inside of the fibers is smooth. These results suggest that fouling primarily occurs on the outside of the membrane (see Figure 80). Oxygen, nitrogen, magnesium, aluminum, silicon, phosphor, sulphur, calcium and iron are detected fouling elements in the SEM-EDS analyses. According to the EDS-mapping of the outside fouling layer, nitrogen, aluminum and phosphor were almost regularly distributed over the fouling layer. Iron was only found at single points. The EDS mapping showed silicon and oxygen as main elements of the fouling (see Figure 81). Diatoms were clearly recognizable. Therefore, biofouling with algae seems to be the most prominent type of fouling.

Figure 79: Black fibrous deposits on the membrane fibers.

Figure 80: SEM image of the membrane, partially covered with a fouling layer (uncovered membrane top left and fouling layer bottom right).

Figure 81: Element distribution of the main elements in the uncovered membrane and the fouling layer.

4.5.3.3 Ultrafiltration backwash and CIP optimization

Initially, the backwash procedure was only triggered after a fixed time interval, allowing the TMP to rise more or less unlimited during the filtration cycle. This was adapted on 25/08/2023, making a trigger based on TMP possible as long as there is enough UF filtrate to carry out the backwash. Throughout the test period, the trigger value was gradually lowered. Out of the tests and discussions with the supplier, the recommendation is made to trigger backwash at 0.2 - 0.3 bar already to avoid accumulation of persistent fouling. Moreover, the filtration cycle time (if the TMP trigger value is not reached) was originally set to 1 hour, which seems to be insufficient. It is recommended to start with

a shorter filtration cycle of 30 minutes and gradually elongate it if possible. This has an impact on the water recovery, as is discussed in Section 4.5.4.1.

As previously mentioned, the backwash process includes an air cleaning procedure (air scour). This process facilitates the detachment of particles adhered to the membrane. Due to the high fouling potential of the WWTP effluent as a source and the subsequent TMP that was observed in the pilot, the supplier recommends extending the air scour step in the backwash procedure (e.g. also use the air scour function during the draining phase and/or the backwash top phase) and to additionally perform this air cleaning manually on a regular basis. The effect of this manual air scour cleaning on the initial TMP is depicted in Table 32.

Table 32: Effect of manual air cleaning of the UF membrane on the initial TMP.

Date	Initial TMP		
	Before air scour (bar)	After Air scour (bar)	Reduction (%)
2/06/2023	1.32	1.25	5.30
3/06/2023	1.25	0.644	48.48
26/06/2023	1.37	1.20	12.41
4/07/2023	1.44	1.2	16.67
14/07/2023	1.38	1.29	6.52
24/07/2023	1.47	1.25	14.97
9/10/2023	1.05	0.917	12.67

From the table, it can be inferred that the impact of this is not significant. This is because the pump responsible for the air scour apparently operates in suction mode rather than in blowing mode because of a switch in electrical phase direction upon installation of the pilot. This irregularity was only discovered at the replacement of the membrane on 25/01/2024. As a result, the intended effect is not achieved. Although the membrane does vibrate, potentially causing particles to loosen somewhat, there is no effective cleaning by air bubbles. The new membrane did not experience the same rate of increase of TMP as the first membrane experienced even in the first months. This might indicate that the air scour is indeed a crucial part of the backwash when applying ultrafiltration on municipal effluent.

An alternative method to reduce the initial TMP of the UF membrane is by performing a CIP procedure or a Mini CIP procedure (same but shorter). The effects of a CIP are demonstrated in Table 33. On 14/12/2023 and 15/12/2023, it was decided to perform an overnight CIP with NaOCl to remove biological contaminants, followed by an acidic CIP with HCl to eliminate inorganic pollution. It is important to perform an acidic CIP immediately after an alkaline CIP.

Table 33: Table : Effect of performing a CIP on the UF membrane on the initial TMP over the UF.

Date	Setpoints	Initial TMP		
		Before CIP (bar)	After CIP (bar)	Reduction (%)
28/07/2023	1500 ppm NaOCl 35°C pH 11	1.4	0.698	50
5/10/2023	1500 ppm NaOCl 35°C pH 11	0.815	0.681	16
14/12/2023 & 15/12/2023	Combination CIP – elongated soaking 1500 ppm NaOCl 35°C pH 11 19h of soaking HCl 35°C pH 2	1.03	0.810	21

The effects of a CIP procedure are noticeable, but the initial TMP of 0.2 bar cannot be sustained in the long term. This suggests that there is a significant degree of contamination that cannot be completely removed through the CIP process. It is recommended to perform a CIP or mini-CIP procedure more frequently. A Mini CIP might best be performed on a weekly basis, or more frequent, if the UF backwash is triggered by the TMP trigger more often (i.e. the filtration cycle of the UF is not finalized anymore). A CIP might best be performed on a monthly basis, or more often, if the mini-CIP is insufficient to restore the original initial TMP.

4.5.3.4 Additional recommendations to enhance ultrafiltration

The use of polyelectrolyte during periods of high secondary effluent turbidity might cause clogging of the membrane pores. To prevent residues of polyelectrolyte to enter the pilot installation, a waiting time of five hours (based on the residence time in the settlers and median flow rates) is applied when polymer has been dosed. However, since the residence time is highly dependent on the instant flow rate and since the assumption of plug flow does not matches real flow in the settler, this precautionary waiting time will not be able to completely prevent polyelectrolyte residues entering the pilot. Considering the advice from the membrane supplier (Dupont) to avoid using cationic polymers, a decision was made on 18/08/2023 to transition from the cationic polymer AQE 84 (Clarflok) to the anionic polymer MK 53 (Clarflok). The sludge settling rate of both polymers is

comparable in case of the WWTP in Woumen, allowing for this transition. In future reuse applications, it can be a no regret measure to check which polymer type causes least risk for membrane fouling and whether the transition is possible.

The quick steady rise of TMP indicates that the load on the membrane is quite high. A more stringent prefiltration, e.g. a 50 µm screen, might be beneficial. However, due to the clogging problems in the prefilter (see Section 4.5.2), this can only be achieved through multi-layer prefiltration to divide the load over multiple filtration steps with decreasing pore size.

At last, some recommendations suggested to enhance prefiltration (see Section 4.5.2.4), might also be beneficial to prevent ultrafiltration fouling, such as minor adaptations to the control and the design of the WWTP and quenching the biological activity through pre-disinfection.

4.5.4 Low water recovery

4.5.4.1 Recovery of the ultrafiltration unit

The theoretical recovery of the ultrafilter is 95%. It is clear that this theoretical recovery cannot be achieved. The feed flow to the UF is 1.8 m³/h but the flow rate to the RO needs to be decreased to 1 m³/h because 1.5 m³/h cannot be met due to the frequent need for prefilter cleaning and backwash. At the end of the test period, it became clear that at rainy days, when the effluent quality is less, even a feed to the RO of 1 m³/h cannot be sustained.

Both more frequent backwashes of the UF and more frequent self-cleaning of the prefilter reduce the recovery of the UF module in this suboptimal design, as is clear from Table 34. An optimized design is needed to contain an acceptable recovery.

Table 34: Recovery of the UF module at varying conditions.

Date	Effluent quality conditions	Optimized backwash and self-cleaning implemented?	Recovery of the UF module (%)
27/04/2023	Good quality conditions	No	82
9/10/2023	Bad quality conditions	No	52
6/02/2024	Good quality conditions	Yes	68
19/02/2024	Bad quality conditions	Yes	41

To achieve a better recovery in the ultrafiltration, some strategies described in Sections 4.5.2.4 and 4.5.3.4, such as the addition of multi-barrier filtration or pre-disinfection are needed.

4.5.4.2 Recovery of the reversed osmosis unit

The recovery of reversed osmosis could not be optimized in this project since the RO unit could not be used to its full capacity because of the limitations of the UF unit. The recovery of RO was fixed to

50% throughout the complete testing period and since 01/06/2023, the flow rate was limited to 1m³/h. No fouling problems occurred with the RO and no biocide or antiscalant had to be dosed. According to the supplier guidelines, a recovery of at least 70% should be achievable. More tests with a suitable UF treatment are necessary to confirm this.

4.5.5 Optimizing the operational strategy

Optimized performance of the pilot installation was at the end of the testing period achieved with the following setup:

- UF feed flow rate of 1.8 m³/h
- prefilter with a 100 µm screen
- Prefilter pressure drop trigger for self-cleaning at 0.35 bar
- UF filtration cycle of 30 minutes
- UF TMP trigger for backwash at 0.2 bar
- RO feed flow rate of 1 m³/h.

These settings work well in dry weather with low turbidity water, but quickly fail in higher turbidity conditions. To further optimize the operation of this technology train, more structural adaptations are needed, which could not be implemented in this pilot setup.

The challenges in the pilot tests cannot be evaluated independently from the functioning of the WWTP. Whether or not reuse becomes a common practice in Flanders in the near future, it is worth to have a critical look at the current design and operation and how it impacts potential reuse activities and the environment.

From these operational challenges, it is clear that only little is known about the practice of dosing polyelectrolyte for settling enhancement in WWTP's. The type is not selected based on eventual post-treatment technologies, waste water operators are unaware of potential (eco)toxicological effects of polymer residues, the dose is not evidence based and is not varied based on temporal variations in quality, and there is no knowledge on overdosing, since residues cannot be analyzed. To overcome these limitations and learn more about polyelectrolyte dosing at their own WWTP's, Aquafin initiated a trajectory together with Olpas (<https://www.olpas.tech/>) to investigate the potential of a novel sensor to determine polyelectrolyte residues in the water phase by means of acoustic impedance. The sensor has successfully passed proof-of-concept testing at lab scale by Olpas and is currently further developed in a real environment at Aquafin. Figure 82 shows the correspondence between known polyelectrolyte concentrations in a dilution series in demineralized water (x-axis) and the predicted concentration from the Olpas sensor signal (y-axis).

Figure 82: Correspondence between dissolved polyelectrolyte concentration in demineralized water and Olpas sensor signal. The blue line represents the 1:1 correlation between the predicted values and the real values. Points above this line are a slight overestimation, points below this line an underestimation.

Given the promising results of these preliminary tests, the trajectory of determining polyelectrolyte concentrations from acoustic sensors will continue after the B-WaterSmart project.

Furthermore, it is clear that, although the WWTP of Woumen is always compliant with discharge and removal standards from European and Flemish legislation, effluent quality can vary a lot. An important aspect influencing treatment effectiveness is the flow rate through the plant, which is correlated strongly with the weather conditions. It is worth evaluating the control and design strategies whether minor actions can be taken to enhance, and mainly stabilize, the effluent quality. This is not that straightforward, since it is not the only aspect to be taken into account. Energy efficiency, resource usage, treatment robustness, etc. are all important criteria that might have conflicting interests in the design or the operational phase.

4.6 Lessons learned

From these tests it can be concluded that effluent reuse is a valid option to enhance the robustness of the drinking water production center in Woumen. The removal efficiency of each purification technology was assessed, and the permeate qualities were compared to drinking water standards, indicating that the combination UF-RO-UV-GAC from initial limited measurements is suitable for drinking water production. The biggest challenges come from nutrients, salts, organic micropollutants and pathogens and the incorporation of RO in the treatment train is assessed to be the best choice.

Although all used technologies are of TRL 9, their application on secondary effluent appeared to be very challenging, mainly concerning clogging and fouling of prefiltration and ultrafiltration. The main challenges were:

- Fluctuating effluent quality and its susceptibility to weather conditions
- Dosage of polyelectrolyte in the treatment train
- The high potential of the water for biofouling, especially during standstill
- Defining proper conditions for self-cleaning and backwash
- Malfunctioning of components with a large impact on the operation

To overcome these challenges, some proposed measures are:

- Add a pre-disinfection step, see Section 4.5.2.4.
- Use a multi-stage prefiltration
- Aim for continuous operation
- Evaluate the design and operational functionalities of the WWTP
- Give special attention to polyelectrolyte dosing
- Do not allow the pressure drop over the prefilter nor the TMP over the UF to rise too much. Incorporate proper self-cleaning and backwash triggers.
- Perform chemical cleaning on a regular basis, more frequent compared to other water sources
- Regularly check critical compartments for malfunctions

5 Potential implementation of CCRO and effluent reuse schemes in water production center De Blankaart

5.1 Model setup and calibration

To evaluate the impact of an additional treatment step and/or alternative feed water, a model was built. This model is a simplified model focusing on the drinking water production process only. To assess the impact of the CCRO and effluent reuse in a regional context, KWR developed the UWOT toolkit. This tool and the results of the regional analysis are described in D3.5. An update of the results for this regional analyses is in preparation (Van Huijgevoort, 2024) The model takes into account historical data for the period 1/1/2015 until 31/7/2023) related to water availability and water quality at the two main water sources for WPC De Blankaart. Intake restrictions are imposed for the parameters chlorides, bentazon and metaldehyde (see Table 35). The model calculates the mass balance over the reservoir on a daily basis. Evaporation is not taken into account. If there is no restriction on water availability and/or water quality, maximum 100,000 m³/day fresh water is pumped to the reservoir. The daily water production is 40,000 m³/day in wintertime and 15,000~m³/day in summer time. In reality, the intake and production strategy are more complex compared to the simplified settings included in the model. Intake strategy and restrictions may vary over time. Figure 83 shows the actual and modelled volume/level in the reservoir. Notwithstanding the simplified intake criteria, the model predicts the typical pattern well. During the wintertime, abundant water is available in the region for intake. The reservoir is in this period almost 100% filled. Starting from spring, water intake becomes limited due to a combination of decreasing water quality and reduced water availability. As production continues and the intake is limited the water level decreases during the summer period. The drop in water level varies over the years and depends on climatological and operational factors. During dry years, the water level decreased to 30 to 50% of maximum capacity. In the period 2016-2018 the decrease of the water level was most pronounced. Afterwards additional measures were taken (improved intake management, reduced production volumes below 15,000 m³/day during droughts) to mitigate drought effects.

Table 35: Overview of criteria used to build the model.

Criterion	Value	action	Source of information	Reason/ description
Chloride concentration at source	> 180 mg/l	No intake	Historical data	Water quality
Bentazon concentration at source	> 0.6 mg/l	No intake	Historical data	

Criterion	Value	action	Source of information	Reason/description
Metaldehyde concentration at source	> 0.2 mg/l	No intake	Historical data	
Water flow IJzer	< 100,000 m ³ /day	Reduced intake (50%)	Data VMM river discharge (Keiem)	Water scarcity
	< 50,000 m ³ /day	No intake		
Blankaartvijver (January until October)	< 2.95 m	No intake	Historical water levels (VMM)	Water scarcity (minimum target level imposed by water authorities) Water scarcity (minimum target level imposed by water authorities)
Blankaartvijver (February until October)	< 2.75 m TAW	No intake	Historical water levels (VMM)	
Blankaartvijver (November)	< 2.85 m TAW	No intake	Historical water levels (VMM)	
Maximum intake	100,000 m ³ /day			Technical limitation intake
Production regime summer	15,000 m ³ /day			Actual production regime
Production regime winter	40,000 m ³ /day			
Water volume in reservoir	<1,200,000 m ³ (less than 40% of maximum capacity)	Production regime max 15,000 m ³ /day		Reduced production to prevent total stop water production

Figure 83: Calibration of the intake model for WPC De Blankaart.

5.2 Technological solutions taken into account

In order to maintain the water production at a minimal level of 15,000 m³/day during long drought periods, additional water sources are required. The two main options considered in B-WaterSmart are

1. Integration of a CCRO unit within the actual drinking water treatment train. The CCRO technology would remove salts (chlorides) and micropollutants. The actual intake criteria can be relaxed due to this additional treatment step and water that is currently considered as off spec can be fed to the reservoir. To generate sufficient impact at least 50% of the daily production capacity needs to be treated by the new CCRO unit, thus the CCRO is designed to produce 20,000 m³ permeate/day. A CCRO system is preferred as only this technology enables to achieve high water recoveries (up to 95%).
2. The effluent of WWTP Woumen as a new water source. The effluent of the WWTP is actually discharged to the local surface water. By building a new reclamation plant composed of technologies such as ultrafiltration and reverse osmosis, the water can be used within the actual drinking water production. The main benefit is that this water source is also available during extreme drought periods. The reclamation plant is designed to produce 5,000 m³ permeate/day in this scenario. Both UF/CCRO technology and conventional UF/RO may be

considered. If the secondary effluent produced by the WWTP of Aquafin is below the design capacity, the production is decreased accordingly.

The two options are visualized in Figure 84.

Figure 84: Visualization of potential integration of additional treatment steps and water sources in the actual drinking water production at the Blankaart.

5.3 Results of impact assessment

Figure 85 shows the expected impact on water availability of the scenario 1 (use off spec water by CCRO technology). The figure shows the fluctuation of the water level in the reservoir both in the actual situation (full line) and after integration of a CCRO unit within the production (dotted line). A minimum level of 700,000 m³ in the reservoir is considered as a critical level for the water production. In the actual situation the model predicts that this critical level is reached in 4 out of 8 years considered. This can be overcome largely with the additional CCRO treatment. Given the relaxed intake criteria, water intake is possible for a longer period in spring and sometimes additional water intake is possible in summertime. The slope of the decreasing water volume is similar before and after integration of the CCRO technology.

Figure 85: Modelled volume in the reservoir after integration of a CCRO unit of 20,000 m³/day within the drinking water production of De Blankaart.

The results of the modelling of scenario 2 (use of WWTP effluent as drinking water source) is visualized in Figure 86. Similar to the CCRO scenario described above, the use of WWTP effluent enables to maintain the drinking water production at 15,000 m³/day. Although the impact of both scenario's is comparable, the mechanism is different. The CCRO enables to prolong the intake period of freshwater. When WWTP effluent is applied, the intake period for freshwater is unchanged and the decreasing tendency starts at the same moment compared with the no action situation. However, as about 5,000 m³/day external water becomes available, less water needs to be extracted from the reservoir. The slope of the decrease changes and water production from the reservoir can continue over a longer period.

Figure 86: Modelled volume in the reservoir after integration of a water source (effluent WWTP) with capacity of maximum 5,000 m³/day within the drinking water production of De Blankaart.

5.4 Cost-Benefit analyses

For the two scenario's described in Figure 84 a cost calculation is performed. Given the actual state of the project, the cost calculations are only a rough estimation and only intended to give an idea of the order of magnitude. As some confidential data are used, only a summary is provided in this report.

5.4.1 Investment costs

A summary of the costs is provided in Table 36. As discussed in section 5.2 the design capacity for the reuse option (5.000 m³/day) is significantly smaller compared with the required capacity for an inline treatment (20.000 m³/day). This is due to the fact that the effluent of the municipal wastewater treatment plant is also available during dry periods. To operate the effluent reuse installation continuously an additional buffer of at least 6 hours is required to overcome the typical day/night pattern of a municipal waste water treatment plant and an ultrafiltration step as pretreatment given the anticipated higher load of suspended solids in the effluent. For the inline treatment it is assumed that the pretreatment of the drinking water production after renovation is sufficient. Based on the

indicative cost calculation it can be concluded that the option of effluent reuse is financially favorable.

In both cases a concentrate stream is produced by the reverse osmosis unit. Given the lack of information on the requirements, no costs are included for a concentrate treatment step or zero liquid discharge installation.

Table 36 : summary of investment costs for two options

Option and design capacity	Reuse Woumen (5.000 m³.day)	CCRO in line (20.000 m³/day)
buffer 6 h	500.000	
Piping Woumen-blankaart	1.520.000	
Piping concentrate		1.200.000
UF	1.150.000	
CCRO or RO installation	1.150.000	4.600.000
Civil works and building	2.400.000	7.200.000
mounting/electrical works	2.300.000	4.600.000
TOTAL	9.020.000	17.600.000

5.4.2 Operational costs

It is understood that the implementation of a membrane treatment step in the drinking water production scheme will cause an additional cost. Typically the operational costs is 0,05 and 0,25 euro/m³ for ultrafiltration and reverse osmosis respectively. As the permeate produced in both cases will also pass the existing treatment plant, these costs add up to the existing costs for drinking water production. As described in section 5.2 both scenario's will also result in a more regional more robust drinking water system and will increase the total volume of drinking water produced in WPC De Blankaart. As the additional treatment costs are partly compensated by less purchased water from other Flemish drinking water utilities (Farys, Vivaqua) or less costs for transportation of water from other more remote production centers, the overall impact on the water costs is unclear. This type of calculations is part of larger strategic water supply plans and within the context of this report, it is not possible to elaborate on this aspect.

6 Overall assessment

6.1 Local implications of upgrading WWTP effluent

The pilot tests at Aquafin show that it is technically feasible to polish WWTP effluent to the desired quality for reuse, given the right combination of technologies. For WWTP Woumen, an elaborate (e.g., multi-step) prefiltration is recommended before the effluent can be treated with membranes. An RO module is essential because it can ensure adequate removal of the micropollutants that are problematic for drinking water production, apart from benzotriazoles (see section 4.4.1).

Besides technical considerations, a number of other issues are to be addressed when implementing reuse of WWTP effluent in Flanders:

- With a new Urban Waste water Treatment Directive (UWWTD) being drafted and implemented, effluent limits for nitrogen and phosphorus will become more stringent for large WWTPs. Additionally, some WWTPs will need to be upgraded with quaternary treatment targeting micropollutants. For the moment, the revised UWWTD is imposing quaternary treatment steps to achieve 80% removal of some indicator substances of micropollutants. It is not yet certain which WWTPs will need to be upgraded with quaternary treatment. As a consequence, WWTPs with stricter nutrient and micropollutant limits will become more attractive for reuse. Since the UWWTD revision is not yet final, it is unclear what the conditions are for upgrading WWTPs with tertiary or quaternary treatment.
- Not all effluent of a WWTP may be available for reuse. Flanders has a so-called system of environmental flows (E-flows) in place, which defines the minimal flowrate the watercourse needs to ensure its ecological health. A practical rule of thumb is that the E-flow equals the 10th flow percentile. E-flows are defined for each watercourse, and the watercourse manager ultimately decides the minimal effluent discharge rate that needs to be guaranteed. For WWTP Woumen, the receiving watercourse (Houtensluisvaart) has no clear flow direction, and therefore no E-flow has been defined. For the relevant section of the Yser river to which the Houtensluisvaart connects, the 10th percentile is 0.9 m³/s. If all effluent of WWTP Woumen would be reused, this lower value would be reached once every 1.36 years, compared to once every 1.67 years without effluent reused. This suggests that the effluent has no sizeable impact on the E-flow, and reuse would likely not cause any ecological issues concerning flow rate. Further negotiations with the relevant water authorities are required to conclude on the limitations for effluent reuse.
- Depending on the watercourse receiving the effluent, other requirements may be set by the watercourse manager. It might for example be required to keep the watercourse navigable. The watercourse manager may therefore decide to increase the minimal flow of effluent that needs to be discharged during summer months. Additionally, for regions sensitive to salinization, this may also lead to increased minimal effluent discharge requirements

- Effluent polishing installations always produce waste streams. In case of backwash waters (e.g., from UF) and CIP waters, these could potentially be recirculated to the WWTP influent. In case of RO concentrate, this would possibly need to be discharged into surface waters or require further treatment. The impact of concentrate discharge needs to be assessed to ensure that the water quality does not deteriorate (cf. Weser arrest (Judgement of 1/07/2015 — Case C-461/13, 2015)) in terms of solids, organics, nutrients, micropollutants, salts, etc.
- Each WWTP has its own technical issues and specific effluent quality, which need to be taken into account early in the planning phase. For example, WWTP Woumen has an issue with high solids concentrations and therefore polyelectrolyte dosage during rainy weather, which has caused issues with the pilot's performance.

6.2 Integrating WWTP effluent in the drinking water scheme

Technologically, it is possible to build an independent drinking water production center for upgrading the WWTP effluent to drinking water and to inject the produced drinking water in the distribution network. Taking into account that a new drinking water production center requires a separate quality control plan and water injection strategy, this may be organizational and economical unfavorable. Specifically, the WWTP of Woumen and the water production center of De Blankaart are located at limited distance from each other. Therefore, as mentioned in Section 4.2.2, it is advised to install a minimal effluent polishing step at WWTP Woumen to upgrade the effluent quality to at least comparable quality standards as applied now for raw surface water intake. To produce drinking water, the existing production capacity can be shared.

The pretreated effluent can be fed in the existing raw water reservoir or be inserted directly in the drinking water treatment line. Based on the technological evaluation and the QMRA-tool developed within WP 3.4 (B-WaterSmart product DAP5), a limited pretreatment (standalone activated carbon or an ultrafiltration) is not sufficient to meet the intake quality for feeding it into the raw water reservoir for components as chloride and micropollutants. The pretreatment of the WWTP effluent requires at least a reverse osmosis step to meet all requirements (see Section 4.2.2). The permeate produced by the reverse osmosis will already be close to drinking water standards. If this water would be fed to the open reservoir, the quality would be downgraded to raw water and therefore, water treatment is needed one more to regain the high quality of RO, wasting energy and resources during the process by upgrading it once more. Although this approach might have some advantages out of risk assessment perspective, it is clearly not sustainable and therefore less desirable. Therefore, it is only preferred when the risks were very high or cannot be controlled by monitoring of the RO performance, which is most likely not the case. Therefore, it is advised to inject the permeate from the WWTP pretreatment reverse osmosis in the existing drinking water production train after the sand filtration. The pretreated water will then pass the post treatment of the drinking water production (Advanced oxidation, active carbon, UV disinfection and chlorination). The full treatment line is composed out of several consecutive treatment technologies to guarantee continuous the

drinking water standards, even if one of the treatment steps would partially fail. This is called the multi-barrier concept.

6.3 Water Smartness' in the Flemish case study

To ensure future drinking water supply in Flanders, over-exploitation of ground water reservoirs needs to be avoided and permits are subject to strict volume limitations. Alternative surface water sources are limited as Flanders has only few large water bodies, and these rivers are subjected to drought and water quality issues. All drinking water utilities are currently preparing water safety plans. These plans are specific for each region, but can contain the following building blocks:

1. Interconnecting regions to be less dependent on local water sources
2. Extend the drinking water production to mitigate emerging pollutants for all surface water production sites
3. Increase (underground) water buffering to store abundant water in winter time for use in drought periods
4. Resource diversification by use of alternative water sources such as WWTP effluent
5. Maximize recharge of ground water reservoirs by local infiltration of rain water
6. Minimize pollution of surface water and groundwater with (micro) pollutants.

These solutions are interdependent, e.g., the implementation of a WWTP effluent reuse scheme (block 4) may reduce the need for water storage (block 3) but may require the proximity of a large transport pipeline (block 1). The work performed in B-WaterSmart contributes to better understanding of the options for building block 2 and 4. The UWOT tool (DAP 4) will support the decision-making process by generating insight in the complex interactions of potential measures.

It is understood that additional treatment steps to make the drinking water production more robust or to use more challenging water sources, will result in additional treatment costs and an increase of the ecological impact (concentrate streams, material use, energy neutrality, CO₂ emissions...) of the drinking water sector. A water smart solution will take all these potentially conflicting impacts into account. The water-smartness assessment framework (WP 6) can be used to assess these challenges and compare potential water-smart approaches in future projects, working towards a water-smart solution for Flanders. The advanced treatment trains are an important element in this water smart solution, but should be restricted to regions with acute water shortage.

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9 Annex 1 : extract from Deliverable 3.5 “the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit -Final release” -

Extract Deliverable 3.5, pagina 155-156

6.2.5.3 QMRA+ results

The QMRA+ tool was used to assess the safety various options for combinations of treatment processes shown in Table 23. Results from the application of QMRA+ tool showed that the current source, the IJzer river, contains significant fecal contamination. Therefore, the post-treatment of effluent for supply to the raw water reservoir can be relatively limited. This wouldn't affect the current contamination level in the reservoir. In most cases the post-treated effluent contained fewer pathogens than the current source. One example of QMRA+ output is shown in Figure 84. The boxplots indicate the variability and uncertainty about the annual risk of infection from treated effluent. This demonstrates that the predicted risk is several orders of magnitude below the health target of 1 infection per 10,000 persons per year as indicated by the red line.

Although chemical risk assessment wasn't part of the study, a typical post treatment system for effluent was evaluated for the effect on microbial drinking water quality. Such an extensive post-treatment would (in theory) be sufficient to directly produce safe drinking water, according to the QMRA+ tool. This demonstrates that integrating microbial and chemical risk assessments is needed to find safe and efficient solutions for effluent reuse.

Limitations of the study were mostly due to the lack of site-specific data on actual pathogen concentrations in the various sources (current river IJzer or effluent) and data on actual treatment performance for pathogen removal and inactivation in the current drinking water system. Obtaining this data would require a long-term monitoring program for pathogens which is costly and therefore not feasible within the constraints of the project. Pilot research to assess the efficacy of post-treatment options for effluent would provide more adequate, site-specific, data for the risk assessment.

Table 23: Studied treatment and supplement options and the assessed risk according to the QMRA+ tool expressed as log of infection per person per year. Values not meeting the Dutch guideline value of 4 are highlighted in red.

Scenario	UF	RO	RO50%	NF	UV	GAC	CONV	iC12	RSF	GAC	C12	DAF	DRSF	AOP	UV	RO	Infectie			4			DALY			6		
																	B	V	P	B	V	P	B	V	P			
1 Effluent huidig- Drinkwater huidig							X	X	X	X	X							2,6	0,7	0,1	5,4	2,8	2,9					
2 Effluent optie1-Drinkwater huidig	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X							19	14	14	22	16	17					
2h Effluent optie UF-UV - Drinkwater huidig	X	0			X	X	X	X	X	X	X							10	6,8	7	13	8,9	9,9					
3h Effluent optie UV - Drinkwater huidig	0		0		X	X	X	X	X	X	X							7,1	4,8	3	10	7	5,9					
16 IJzer-Blankaart-Drinkwater huidig							X	X	X	X	X							4,1	1,3	3,2	7	3,4	6,2					
17 IJzer-Blankaart-Drinkwater nieuw											2X	X	X	X	X	X		6,4	5,4	4,8	9,3	7,5	7,7					
18 Effluent-RSF- Drinkwater nieuw			RSF								2X	X	X	X	X	X		7,2	5,2	3,5	10	7,4	6,5					
19 Effluent-NF-Drinkwater nieuw				X							2X	X	X	X	X	X		12	11	8,3	14	12	11					

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